

Agro2Circular

D7.15 – Financing Recommendations

March 2025

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Table of contents

List of Tables	9
List of abbreviations	10
1 Executive Summary	13
2 Introduction	14
3 International Financing Schemes for the Circular Economy	18
3.1 European Union Funds	18
3.1.1 Horizon Europe	19
3.1.2 Regional Policy Support	21
3.1.3 Interreg Europe	23
3.1.4 LIFE	24
3.1.5 Single Market Programme	25
3.2 Financial Institutions	26
3.2.1 World Bank Group	27
3.2.2 European Investment Bank	29
3.2.3 Joint Initiative on Circular Economy	31
3.2.4 European Bank for Reconstruction and Development	32
3.3 International Private Investments and other Private Funding Opportunities	33
3.3.1 Asset Management Firms	33
3.3.2 Investment Funds	35
3.3.3 Crowdfunding	36
4 Green Public Procurement	39
5 Public Financing Schemes in the Region of Murcia	43
5.1 INFO	43
5.1.1 Grant programme for energy efficiency actions in SMEs and large companies in the industrial sector	43

5.1.2	HSOS grant line for the calculation and certification of carbon footprint in organisation/product and water footprint.....	44
5.1.3	Innovation voucher for optimising industrial processes and products eco-innovation	45
5.1.4	R&D support to regional technological centres for developing sustainable products and processes.....	46
5.1.5	R&D support to enterprises for developing sustainable products and processes	46
5.2.	CARM	46
5.2.1	Subsides to operational funds of fruit and vegetable producer organisations (FVPOs).....	47
5.2.2	Establishment and operation of Innovation and Environmental Adaptation (IEA) Task Forces	48
5.1.6	Subsides for investments in agricultural holdings.....	48
5.1.7	Aid for the creation of agricultural enterprises by young farmers.....	49
5.1.8	Grants for investment in processing, marketing and development of agricultural products	49
5.1.9	Grants for the consolidation of irrigation by using reclaimed water from wastewater reservoirs.....	50
5.1.10	Grant for the improvement of energy efficiency and renewable energy generation in irrigation communities. RDP 2014-2022 / IRUE Funds. Call for proposals 2024	50
6	Private Financing Schemes in the Region of Murcia	52
6.1	Bank and Financial Cooperatives Schemes.....	52
6.2	Alternative Private Financing Schemes in the Region of Murcia	59
6.2.1.	Venture Capital (VC).....	59
6.2.2.	Private Equity.....	59
6.2.3.	Crowdfunding.....	60
6.2.4.	Angel Investors	60
7	Financing Schemes & Agro2Circular Business Models	62

8	Good Practices	71
8.1	CIRCWASTE (Finland).....	71
8.2	URBIOFIN (Greece).....	72
8.3.	Circular Economy for Businesses (Murcia, Spain).....	73
8.4.	EIB Financed Projects.....	75
8.4.1.	Novamont Renewable Chemistry, Italy	75
8.4.2.	ISP Loan for Circular Economy, Italy.....	76
8.4.3.	IREN Climate Action and Circular Economy Loan, Italy	76
8.4.4.	Winnow, Romania	77
8.4.5.	Tackling Food Waste, France.....	77
8.5.	De Clique (Netherlands).....	77
8.6.	GPP Good Practices.....	78
8.6.1.	GPP in Flemish Governments Cooperation Agreement with Municipalities .	78
8.6.2.	GPP Regional Plan, Liguria.....	79
8.6.3.	Promotion of Green Public Procurement by Providing Green Technical Specifications, Lithuania	80
8.6.4.	Good Practices in Green Public Procurement in Regional Waste Management, Spain	80
8.7.	Good Financial Practices of Banks in the Region of Murcia	81
8.7.1.	Cajamar Cooperative Group.....	81
8.7.2.	CaixaBank.....	83
8.7.3.	BBVA.....	83
8.7.4.	Unicaja Banco	84
9	Financing Recommendations	85
9.1.	Circular Economy Overview & Challenges	85
9.2.	Financing & Investment for Circular Economy.....	85
9.3.	Business Models & Market Considerations	87
9.4.	Role of Technology & Innovation in Circular Economy.....	87
9.5.	Investment Priorities for Sustainability	87
9.6.	Green Public Procurement (GPP) & Sustainable Procurement.....	88

10 Conclusions	90
11 Bibliography	92

List of Tables

Table 1 - World Bank Group Municipal Solid Waste Management Operations by Country Income Group	29
Table 2 - EIB Circular Economy Signed Operations, 2015-2019	30
Table 3 - Main Bank and Cooperative Bank Financing Mechanism	53
Table 4 - Sources of Equity Capital and Company's Stage of Development	60
Table 5 - The Impact of Circular Business Models on a Linear Economy	63
Table 6 - Circular Business Impact on the Economy Value Chain	64

List of abbreviations

BBI JU	Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking
BBVA	Banco Bilbao Vizcaya Argentaria
BGK	Bank Gospodarstwa Krajowego
C3	Circular City Centre
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CARM	Comunidad Autónoma Región de Murcia
CDC	Caisse des Dépôts Groupe
CDP	Cassa Depositi e Prestiti
CE	Circular Economy
CF	Cohesion Fund
CPO LT	Central Procurement Organisation
CREA	Consortio para la Gestión de Residuos de Vinalopó
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
EAGF	European Agricultural Guarantee Fund
EAFRD	European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development
EBRD	European Bank for Reconstruction and Development
EC	European Commission
ECBF	European Circular Bioeconomy Fund
EEN	Enterprise Europe Network
EFSI	European Fund for Strategic Investments
EGFF	European Growth Finance Facility
EIAH	European Investment Advisory Hub
EIB	European Investment Bank
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ESG	Environmental, Social and Governance
ESIF	European Structural and Investment Funds
ETC	European Territorial Cooperation
EU	European Union
EURI	European Union Recovery Instrument
FVPOs	Subsides to operational funds of fruits and vegetables producer organisations

GEF	Global Environment Facility
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GLP	Green Loan Principles
GNI	Gross National Income
GO	Agri EIP Operational Group
GPP	Green Public Procurement
IBRD	International Bank for Reconstruction and Development
ICO	Instituto de Crédito Oficial
ICSID	International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes
IDAE	Instituto para la Diversificación y Ahorro de la Energía
IFC	International Finance Corporation
INFO	Instituto de Fomento de la Región de Murcia
JICE	Joint Initiative on the Circular Economy
JTF	Just Transition Fund
JRC	Joint Research Center
KETs	Key Enabling Technologies
KfW	Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau
MAPA	Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food
MDB	Multilateral Development Banks
MIGA	Multilateral Investment Guarantee Agency
MSW	Municipal Solid Waste
MSWM	Municipal Solid Waste Management
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NPV	Net Present Value
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
RDA	Regional Development Agency
R&D	Research and Development
SAPs	Standard Action Projects
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SIPs	Strategic Integrated Projects
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SMP	Single Market Programme

UN	United Nations
VC	Venture Capital
WBG	World Bank Group
WP	Work Package

1 Executive Summary

This document is a synthesis report summarizing the main conclusions regarding financing schemes and recommendations for their improvement within the Agro2Circular (A2C) project. The report aims to provide an overview of the key funding mechanisms that can partially or fully support businesses and projects in the circular economy, focusing on both public and private financing sources at the European and regional levels.

The analysis explores major European Union funding programs, such as Horizon Europe, the LIFE Programme, and regional development funds, alongside international financial institutions, national grants, private investments, and alternative financing models such as crowdfunding. Additionally, the report examines Green Public Procurement (GPP) as a key financial driver to stimulate investment in circular economy solutions.

Key findings indicate that substantial EU funding remains available for circular economy projects, but challenges persist, particularly for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs), due to high perceived risks, long payback periods, and administrative complexities in accessing financial support. Furthermore, regional disparities in funding accessibility highlight the need for tailored financing strategies to support the implementation of circular business models.

To improve financing schemes, the report provides targeted recommendations, including enhancing private sector involvement through impact investing and blended finance models, simplifying funding application procedures, standardizing reporting frameworks to improve financial transparency, and expanding GPP to drive circular investments. These recommendations aim to strengthen the financial ecosystem supporting the adoption, scalability, and replicability of circular systemic solutions, ensuring long-term sustainability and economic viability.

2 Introduction

The world has reached a tipping point where it can no longer cope with the numerous human-made environmental pressures and triple planetary crisis of climate change, environmental pollution, and biodiversity loss. According to Earth Overshoot Day data, the last occasion on which the world was able to sustain itself occurred in December 1971. In 2023, however, all renewable resources were depleted by the 2nd of August.¹ The famous 1972 Club of Rome report gave the issue a succinct and pragmatic slogan: The Limits to Growth².

It is no longer an option: the world must become more sustainable. One of the proposed models that enable the shift to a more sustainable future is the circular economy, as the necessary changes to resource exhaustion are not achievable within today's linear economic approach. The prevailing economic model is based on the linear function of extraction – production – usage – disposal. In contrast, the circular economy aims to repair, reuse, and recycle today's valuable, but scarce, materials and resources. This is a fact that is also increasingly acknowledged by policymakers around the world.

In that sense, the European Union announced its first Action Plan for the Circular Economy in 2015 and has since initiated a subsequent plan as part of its European Green Deal. This new plan consisting of 35 actions³, emphasises that economic growth can be achieved independently of resource consumption.

Global events have highlighted the urgent need for more sustainable patterns of production and consumption. One such event was the Covid-19 pandemic, which disrupted supply chains and exposed the manifold issues connected to the transport of materials over long

¹ Earth Overshoot Day, "Home," [Online]. Available: <https://www.overshootday.org/>

² D. H. Meadows, D. L. Meadows, J. Randers, and W. W. Behrens III, "The Limits to Growth: A Report for the Club of Rome's Project on the Predicament of Mankind", Universe Books, 1972. [Online]. Available: https://collections.dartmouth.edu/teitexts/meadows/diplomatic/meadows_ltg-diplomatic.html

³ European Commission, "A new Circular Economy Action Plan: For a cleaner and more competitive Europe," COM(2020) 98 final. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1583933814386&uri=COM:2020:98:FIN>

distances. Reassessing and refocussing on internal resources also enables nations and regions to contribute to a more efficient use of resources and the reduction of transport-related emissions. Additionally, the Russian full-scale war against Ukraine, which began in February 2022, has sparked intense debates about strategic autonomy and the need for a resource-independent Europe – objectives that can be better achieved through a circular economy.

Although the transition to a circular economy is urgently needed, numerous barriers still exist. One of such barriers pertains to access to finance for circular economy models, largely attributable to the perception and assessment of risks, despite the present growth in financial interest in investing in circular economy business opportunities.⁴ Circular economy business models often require higher investment costs due to the necessity of establishing an infrastructure. This problem is especially acute for SMEs, who are unable to make large investments themselves and face reluctance from banks to finance circular economy initiatives with a long payback period. The lower return of circular economy in comparison to linear business models is largely due to the unpricing positive and negative externalities, i.e., the negative effects of linear products are frequently not priced in.⁵ Additionally, the absence of reliable data on which to base financing decisions, as reporting standards for circular solutions that show their benefits are still in their infancy.

However, the circular economy offers investment opportunities, not only because it is a proven policy response to pressing environmental and social challenges, but also for investment reasons. A study conducted by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation concluded that in addition to increasing the resilience of supply chains, the circular economy also offers significant growth opportunities. Adopting circular economy principles in Europe in the mobility, built environment and food sectors alone could generate annual benefits of €1.8

⁴ European Union, "Financing the circular economy," [Online]. Available: <https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/en/financing-circular-economy>

⁵ Neosfer, "Financing Circular Economy," 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://neosfer.de/en/financing-circular-economy/>

trillion by 2030.⁶ Furthermore, the circular economy promises a competitive advantage to manufacturing firms by reducing their reliance on materials and components.

The transition to the circular economy will require significant financial resources, from both the public and private sectors and “incentives are vital to overcome barriers stemming from linear models”⁷. There are several incentives that policy makers may implement with the goal to stimulate circular economy that can benefit investors in the transition process. Barriers that need to be overcome and that can be targeted by incentives include market failures preventing or delaying circular products, services and solutions, non-pricing of negative externalities, and the steering of markets towards sustainability and promoting behavioural change. As noted in a report by the European Commission: “incentives have the capacity to create value, reduce the risk of investment and improve the competitiveness of value chains that deliver net environmental benefits compared to linear economies.”⁸

The mechanisms for meeting the finance needs of the circular economy and for reorienting capital from linear to circular solutions are becoming increasingly diverse. The primary catalyst for accelerating the transition to a circular economy include European Union funds, other global grants, instruments created by financial institutions, asset management funds, and the benefits of scaling up green public procurement practices are the main drivers for accelerating the transition to a circular economy. Other financial products and services that have been identified as contributing to this transition include public equity funds, bonds, private market funds, banking, and crowdfunding.⁹

This document constitutes Deliverable 7.15 *Financing Recommendations* of the Agro2Circular project, developed within Task 7.5 *Multidimensional Model for Adoption, Replicability, and Scalability of the A2C Systemic Solution at Regional and EU Level*. It represents the main outcome of Sub-task 7.5.3 *Financing Schemes Linked to the Business*

⁶ Ellen MacArthur Foundation, "Financing the Circular Economy: Capturing the Opportunity," 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://emf.thirdlight.com/file/24/Om5sTEKOn0YUK.Om7xpOm-gdwc/Financing%20the%20circular%20economy%20-%20Capturing%20the%20opportunity.pdf>

⁷ European Commission, "Incentives to Boost the Circular Economy," 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/51378e0a-d303-11eb-ac72-01aa75ed71a1>

⁸ Ibid.

⁹ Ellen MacArthur Foundation, "Financing the circular economy," [Online]. Available: <https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/topics/finance/overview>

Models Generated. *Work Package 7 (WP7)* focuses on ensuring the adoption and scalability of the Agro2Circular systemic solution by addressing key factors such as public engagement, environmental and socio-economic assessment, and financial sustainability. Within this framework, Task 7.5 analyses business models and the financial mechanisms required for their implementation at both territorial and European levels.

This document presents the final version of the financing recommendations, following an initial draft submitted midway through the project in month 18 (March 2023).

Accordingly, the present document concentrates its analysis and recommendations principally on international and regional financial frameworks that enable the circular economy. In addition, the deliverable aligns its analysis and recommendations with the concrete outcomes and results of the Agro2Circular, an EU (H2020) funded project that implements a territorial, scalable, systemic and digitally powered solution for the upcycling of fruits and vegetables residues and non-renewable, multilayer plastic into high added value products. The document is structured into dedicated sections, which present both public and private financing schemes in the region of Murcia, as it is the territorial centre of the Agro2Circular project.

Chapter III explores international financing schemes for the circular economy, with a particular focus on the various funding programmes provided by the European Union. Other points of interest are international financial institutions and other for-profit initiatives, asset management firms and crowdfunding opportunities. Chapter IV then focuses on green public procurement as key mechanism in enabling the transition towards the circular economy. Chapters V and VI present the above-mentioned public and private financing schemes in the Spanish region of Murcia. Chapter VIII is a selection of good financing practices, while, lastly, chapter IX provides the name-giving financing recommendations and overall conclusions.

3 International Financing Schemes for the Circular Economy

3.1 European Union Funds

The European Union has long been considered a pioneer in environmental protection since the von der Leyen Commission announced the European Green Deal in 2019. The declared goal of the Green Deal is to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050 and to decouple economic growth from resource use. An ambitious goal for which the European Commission has identified the circular economy as a key to success, a term that first appeared in the late 1980s and was used by David Pearce and Kerry Turner in 1990 to describe an economic system around the valorisation of waste.¹⁰ Notwithstanding the fact that no finite definition of the circular economy exists, the definition provided by the European Union can provide guidance for the purposes of this document:

“Circular economy is a system which maintains the value of products, materials and resources in the economy for as long as possible and minimises the generation of waste.”¹¹

The circular economy is increasingly being embraced by policy makers worldwide, particularly in Europe, as a key strategy to respond to the unprecedented environmental challenges of the 21st century. In Europe, the Circular Economy Actions Plans, adopted in 2015 and 2020, provide the main policy framework guiding this transition. Reflecting its commitment, the EU has allocated 30% of its €1,074.3 billion Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) for 2021-2027 to climate-related initiatives. Similarly, over €800 billion from the EU's Next Generation Recovery Plan is directed towards green transformation

¹⁰ D. W. Pearce and R. K. Turner, “Economics of Natural Resources and the Environment”, Harvester Wheatsheaf, 1990.

¹¹ European Union, “Circular economy”. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/glossary/circular-economy.html>

efforts.¹² As a result, substantial EU funding is currently available to support the shift to a circular economy.

The European Union supports stakeholders who want to research or invest in this field through various funding programmes, such as the Horizon Europe programme, regional policy support, the LIFE programme, and the Single Market programme. Following the 2024 elections, the new Parliament and Commission have maintained Green Deal commitments while shifting toward a focus on “competitive sustainability” and resilience. Funding remains stable, with Horizon Europe dedicating a significant share to circular economy innovation, LIFE maintaining strong support for environmental projects, and cohesion policy allocating substantial investments to regional circular initiatives.

3.1.1 Horizon Europe

The main source of funding for research and innovation projects in Europe is Horizon Europe, the successor programme to Horizon 2020 in the MFF 2021-2027 and the largest European R&I funding programme to date with a budget of €95.5 billion. In line with the overarching policy strategy of the twin transition, Horizon Europe's stated objectives are to “tackle climate change, help to achieve the UN's Sustainable Development Goals and boost the EU's competitiveness and growth.”¹³ Participation is open to legal entities from the EU and associated countries.

Horizon Europe offers extensive and diverse funding opportunities. Its civilian component is divided into three pillars: Excellence Science, Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness, and Innovative Europe, each further subdivided into funding areas and/or managing authorities. These three pillars are connected by the program section “*Widening Participation and Strengthening the European Research Area*.”¹⁴ While Pillar I “*Excellent Science*”, supports research, and Pillar III “*Innovative Europe*”, supports innovation, Pillar II

¹² European Council, "Long-term EU budget 2021–2027," *Online*. Available: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/the-eu-budget/long-term-eu-budget-2021-2027/>

¹³ European Commission, "Horizon Europe," [Online]. Available: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe_en

¹⁴ European Commission, *Horizon Europe: Investing to Shape Our Future*, 2021. [Online]. Available: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-06/ec_rtd_he-investing-to-shape-our-future_0.pdf

“*Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness*” focuses on developing technologies across six clusters.

In the context of this report, the latter pillar – Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness – is particularly relevant. However, regarding corporate technology adoption, it is important to note that 70% of the Horizon Europe budget for SMEs is allocated to the European Innovation Council, a “one-stop shop” designed to “support to innovations with breakthrough and disruptive nature and scale up potential that are too risky for private investors”¹⁵.

Another key change in Horizon Europe compared to Horizon 2020, alongside the European Innovation Council, are the EU Missions, which are cross-disciplinary “portfolios of actions” designed to support the EU’s strategic priorities, like, for example, the European Green Deal.¹⁶ In addition to funding programmes, an action portfolio can also include, for example, policies and regulations.

The five main mission areas are:

1. *Adaptation to climate change, including societal transformation* – By 2030, the goal is to prepare Europe to deal with climate disruptions, accelerate the transition to a healthy and prosperous future within safe planetary boundaries and scale up resilience solutions that will trigger transformations in society.
2. *Cancer* – By 2030, the mission aims to save more than 3 million additional lives, extend and improve quality of life, achieve a thorough understanding of cancer, prevent avoidable cases, optimise diagnosis and treatment, support the well-being of all individuals affected by cancer, and ensure equitable access to these advancements across Europe.

¹⁵ Ibid.

¹⁶ European Commission, “EU Missions in Horizon Europe,” [Online]. Available: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe_en

3. *Healthy oceans, seas, coastal & inland waters* – By 2030, objectives include cleaning marine and freshwaters ecosystems, restoring degraded habitats, and decarbonising the blue economy to sustainably harness the essential goods and services these ecosystems provide.
4. *Climate-neutral & smart cities* – By 2030, the goals are to support, promote and showcase 100 European cities in their systemic transformation toward climate neutrality, turning them into innovation hubs that enhance quality of life and sustainability in Europe.
5. *Soil health & food* – By 2030, at least 75% of all soils in the EU should be healthy for food production, people, nature and climate. The mission combines research and innovation, education and training, investments and the demonstration of good practices using “Living labs” (experiments and innovation in a laboratory on the ground) and “Lighthouses” (sites showcasing good practices).¹⁷

Although all these missions are related in some way to the circular economy approach, there are concrete opportunities for action in this area, particularly under Missions 1, 4 and 5.

3.1.2 Regional Policy Support

Alongside Horizon Europe, regional policy support is another major instrument for financing the circular economy in the EU, as it can contribute to “increased recycling, improved waste management, resource and energy efficiency, strengthening the bioeconomy, novel product design solutions, new business models and green job creation”¹⁸.

These policy supports were commonly known as “European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF)” in the previous programming period. For the 2021-2027 period, efforts have been made to simplify and yet expand these funds. The main funds to be mentioned for the

¹⁷ European Commission, "Horizon Europe - Investing to shape our future," *Fact sheet*, 2021. [Online]. Available: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-06/ec_rtd_he-investing-to-shape-our-future_0.pdf

¹⁸ European Union, "Financing the circular economy," [Online]. Available: <https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/en/financing-circular-economy>

purposes of this report are the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and the Cohesion Fund (CF), as well as the Just Transition Fund (JTF).

For the period 2021-2027, the EU's regional or cohesion policy identified 5 priorities with a total allocated budget of €392 billion (compared to the 11 thematic objectives of the previous funding period):

1. A more competitive and smarter Europe,
2. A greener, low carbon transitioning towards a net zero carbon economy,
3. A more connected Europe by enhancing mobility,
4. A more social and inclusive Europe,
5. A Europe closer to citizens by fostering the sustainable and integrated development of all types of territories.¹⁹

The list of bodies and organisations that can benefit from regional funding includes public bodies, certain private sector organisations (especially small businesses), universities, associations, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) and voluntary organisations. Foreign companies located in the region of the respective operational programme can also apply, provided they comply with European public procurement rules.

Funding via the European Regional Development Fund operates under a system of shared responsibility between the European Commission and national or regional authorities in Member States. As part of this framework, all regions and Members States based on their level of prosperity, are required to focus their support on building a more competitive and smarter Europe, as well as greener, low-carbon economy and more resilient Europe. This approach is implemented through the mechanism known as 'thematic concentration'." At least 30% of all ERDF operations are expected to contribute to climate objectives.²⁰

In contrast, the Cohesion Fund specifically targets the less developed Member States, defined as those with a Gross National Income (GNI) per capita below 90% of the EU-27

¹⁹ European Commission, "New Cohesion Policy," [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/2021-2027_en

²⁰ European Commission, "European Regional Development Fund," [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/funding/erdf_en

average. Currently, the Cohesion Fund covers Bulgaria, the Czech Republic, Estonia, Greece, Croatia, Cyprus, Latvia, Lithuania, Hungary, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia and Slovenia. It is expected that 37% of the total Cohesion Fund allocation will contribute to climate objectives.²¹

The Just Transition Fund is a new instrument of Cohesion Policy 2021-2027 designed to support the territories most affected by the transition to climate neutrality. Its aim is to reduce regional and structural inequalities across European Regions, while at the same time promoting a green transition.²²

Considering the relevance of circularity for achieving the key objectives of the EU in terms of climate policies, under cohesion policy programmes an investment of 12,5 billion euros is allocated for circular economy and waste management, with 8.6 billion euros coming from EU funds. Although one of the main priorities of this budget is to fund circular waste management initiatives, there is also a focus on promoting a change in consumption patterns and on raising awareness of the necessity of a circular transition.²³ Previous initiatives funded within that framework include research projects with a focus on circular management of water or projects focusing on raising awareness and education on re-using food waste.²⁴

3.1.3 Interreg Europe

Another instrument that supports European regional policy is Interreg Europe, part of the European Territorial Cooperation (ETC) framework. Specifically, it falls under the third component of ETC, known as “European Territorial Cooperation” (often referred to as the “C-part” of ETC), which aims to enhance the effectiveness of Cohesion Policy by fostering cooperation between regions and countries.

²¹ European Commission. “European Regional Development Fund”.

https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/funding/cohesion-fund_en

²² European Commission, “Just Transition Fund,” [Online]. Available:

https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/funding/just-transition-fund_en

²³ European Union, “Cohesion policy support to the circular economy”, [Online]. Available:

<https://cohesiondata.ec.europa.eu/stories/s/21-27-Circular-economy/t6h5-3fup/>

²⁴ Ibid.

Interreg Europe is an interregional cooperation programme co-financed by the European Union that aims to reduce disparities in development, growth, and quality of life within and between European regions. It covers all 27 EU Member States, as well as Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Moldova, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Norway, Serbia, Switzerland and Ukraine. With a budget of €379 million, it supports local, regional and national governments across Europe to develop and implement better policies for the 2021-2027 period. One of its main thematic priorities is ‘Greener Europe’, with a special focus on the circular economy. It contributes to all EU priorities and aims to improve regional governance through capacity building.

Public bodies such as national, regional and local authorities, as well as organisations relevant to regional development policy, such as regional development agencies, innovation agencies, chambers of commerce, environmental agencies, energy agencies, NGOs, universities and/or research centres can benefit from this programme.²⁵

3.1.4 LIFE

In 1992, the European Union created a dedicated financial instrument to fund environmental and climate action – the LIFE programme. In the current funding period (2021-2027), it has been allocated a budget of €5.4 billion and consists of four sub-programmes:

1. Nature and Biodiversity
2. Circular Economy and Quality of Life
3. Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation
4. Clean Energy Transition²⁶

The Circular Economy and Quality of Life sub-programme has been allocated €1.3 billion and is designed to support the shift towards a more “sustainable, circular, toxic-free, energy-efficient and climate-resilient economy”. It also aims to safeguard, restore, and enhance

²⁵ Interreg Europe, "What is Interreg Europe?" [Online]. Available: <https://www.interregeurope.eu/what-is-interreg-europe>

²⁶ European Commission, "LIFE Programme", [Online]. Available: https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/life_en

environmental quality, either through direct interventions or by supporting the integration of those objectives in other policies.”²⁷

The mechanisms of funding are the Standard Action Projects (SAPs) and Strategic Integrated Projects (SIPs). The former targets projects implementing innovation or best practices solutions, while the latter targets policy and legislation actions.

3.1.5 Single Market Programme

The Single Market is one of the central pillars of the European Union and the largest market in the world that enables the free movement of people, goods, services and money among its members. Following those principles, the Commission has proposed “a dedicated €4.2 billion programme for the period of 2021-2027 to empower and protect consumers and enable Europe’s many small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to thrive”.²⁸ The objectives of the Single Market Program (SMP) are to:

1. Maintain a high level of food safety;
2. Give even higher protection to consumers;
3. Boost the competitiveness of businesses, in particular SMEs;
4. Improve the governance of the Single Market and compliance with rules;
5. Produce and disseminate high-quality statistics;
6. Develop effective European standards.²⁹

Of particular relevance to the objective of this deliverable is the focus of this programme on improving the competitiveness and sustainability of European SMEs, especially in areas such as access to European markets or promoting their modernisation to meet global

²⁷ European Union, "Circular economy and quality of life," [Online]. Available:

https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/life/circular-economy-and-quality-life_en

²⁸ European Commission, "Single Market Programme," *Fact sheet*, 2021. [Online]. Available:

<https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/45590>

²⁹ Ibid.

challenges.³⁰ Given the importance the Commission attaches to the transition to a circular economy, any SME focusing on this area would certainly be eligible for financial support under this programme. Furthermore, this programme offers not only financial support, but also advice and recommendations in areas such as access to the single market and achieving a high level of competitiveness, digitalisation or access to finance and EU funding.³¹

3.2 Financial Institutions

The circular economy model offers a variety of financing options. Financial institutions contribute by providing financing and investment for circular economy projects, taking into account the profitability and risks of participation. The implementation of this emerging economic model leads to the development of innovative business mechanisms, as well as tools and new ways to assess the risks of the actions undertaken. The financial sector is increasingly demanding these mechanisms, moving away from the old vision of maximising corporate value by increasing share prices and towards a point of view that considers social and environmental impacts³².

Financial markets have produced various concepts over the decades. In the 80s and 90s, concepts such as portfolio investment, cost economics and corporate governance, reputation, and profitability, among others, became increasingly important. In recent years, all these terms have evolved, with a growing focus on impact investment, sustainability, social and ethical investment, climate and responsible finance and green bonds.

Financial institutions are now being encouraged to participate and invest in circular economy projects in order to achieve the goals set out in the Paris Agreement on climate change. The circular economy system has been introduced over the last years through various financial

³⁰ European Commission, "Single Market Programme: Support to businesses", [Online]. Available: https://commission.europa.eu/funding-tenders/find-funding/eu-funding-programmes/single-market-programme/overview/support-businesses_en

³¹ Ibid.

³² European Commission, "Accelerating the Transition to the Circular Economy: Improving access to finance for circular economy projects," *Report*, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/02590134-4548-11e9-a8ed-01aa75ed71a1>

instruments such as green bonds, which have played a crucial role in accelerating the transition to a circular economic model.

The main financial instruments supporting this transition include:

- Green bonds: Aim to support and finance sustainable and environmentally friendly projects with major issuers such as the World Bank Group. An example is the TSKB Green Bond Issue³³.
- Green credits: Instruments used by banks to finance projects dealing with high levels of pollution in order to reduce the carbon emissions generated, and to finance energy efficiency in line with the targets set by the EU. One example of this is the World Bank's US\$ 212.5 loan to VPBank in Vietnam³⁴.
- Green Exchanges: These are aimed at investors who have an interest in investing in and acquiring shares in environmentally friendly companies. This is the case with the Luxembourg Green Exchange, a platform created to contribute to the goals of the Paris Agreement³⁵.
- Social Bonds: Debt instruments that focus on financing social and humanitarian projects by helping the neediest communities. Some of the areas where these bonds are used are employment, utilities such as access to drinking water or education.

3.2.1 World Bank Group

The World Bank Group (WBG) is the world's largest international organisation for financing developing countries. The World Bank not only provides loans but also offers advice and expertise on a wide range of topics such as climate or human capital. It is integrated into

³³ TSKB, *TSKB Sustainable Finance Framework*, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.tskb.com.tr/uploads/file/tskb-sustainable-finance-framework.pdf>

³⁴ Vietnam Plus, "VPBank, Proparco Cooperate to Promote Green Credit in Vietnam," 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://en.vietnamplus.vn/vpbank-proparco-cooperate-to-promote-green-credit-in-vietnam/185249.vnp>

³⁵ United Nations Climate Change, "The Luxembourg Green Exchange | Luxembourg," [Online]. Available: <https://unfccc.int/climate-action/momentum-for-change/financing-for-climate-friendly-investment/luxembourg-green-exchange>

five international organisations, each with a specific purpose. These include the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (IBRD), the International Development Association (IDA), the International Finance Corporation (IFC), the Multilateral Investment Guarantee Agency (MIGA) and the International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID).

The WBG has increased its commitment regarding Municipal Solid Waste Management (MSWM) in a circular economy. Under the Climate Change Action Plan 2021-2025, which presents significant differences concerning the previous action plan, the WBG aims to find the best way to integrate both waste management and circular economy plans in order to contribute to the development of countries and regions, especially those with high poverty rates, through the implementation of climate change mitigation strategies, and to help meeting the Sustainable Development Goals set by the United Nations in the 2030 Agenda. The IFC, as a member of the WBG, contributes by helping countries and regions with limited infrastructure or informal economies, such as Uganda, to strengthen their potential for municipal solid waste management while increasing prosperity through recovery solutions and financing.

The WBG is considered the main source of lending in the area of municipal solid waste management. The World Bank's internal report on an assessment of the WBG's support to its client countries indicates a contribution of around \$3 billion over the period 2010 to 2020, representing 10% of the total.³⁶ These figures are higher than those of other multilateral development banks, whose funding for similar activities over the same period ranged from 0.5% to 6.1% of the total.

The following table, which is part of the report for the period 2010-2020, shows that low-income countries receive very little or no share of World Bank loans and investments. Lower-middle-income countries and upper-middle-income countries on the other hand, receive the largest share.

³⁶ World Bank, *Annual Report 2022: Helping Countries Adapt to a Changing World*, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/bitstream/handle/10986/37972/AR2022EN.pdf>

Income Group	World Bank Lending			IFC Investment			IFC Advisory		
	Countries	Commitments		Countries	Commitments		Countries	Commitments	
	(no.)	(US\$, millions)	(%)	(no.)	(US\$, millions)	(%)	(no.)	(US\$, millions)	(%)
HIC	1	22	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
UMIC	11	616	34	4	382	96	11	113	50
LMIC	21	1,145	63	3	16	4	5	92	40
LIC	4	28	15	0	0	0	2	24	10
Total	37	1,811	100	7	398	100	18	229	100

Source: Independent Evaluation Group.

Note: FY - fiscal year; HIC - high-income country; IFC - International Finance Corporation; LIC - low-income country; LMIC - lower-middle-income country; UMIC - upper-middle-income country.

Table 1: World Bank Group Municipal Solid Waste Management Operations by Country Income Group.

3.2.2 European Investment Bank

Of all financial institutions, the European Investment Bank (EIB) is the largest multilateral financial institution in the world. It provides financial support and advisory services to meet the needs of businesses in areas such as climate, cohesion, innovation, SMEs, and sustainability, particularly in relation to circular economy projects inside and outside the EU. These projects focus on preventing waste through reuse, recycling, and regeneration of natural systems³⁷. They are implemented through the European Fund for Strategic Investments (EFSI)³⁸, which aims to drive long-term economic growth and improve competitiveness within the EU through private investment.

In addition, the EIB provides advisory support for small businesses, through its InvestEU Advisory Hub, which helps companies to better understand investment and financing opportunities within the EU. This initiative also provides investors and project promoters with information in terms of strategic, market, and project development. Therefore, the main objective of this initiative is to boost investment and innovation, which is directly relevant for the development of circular economy initiatives.³⁹ For instance, the Circular City Centre (C3) is an initiative in where the EIB participates alongside the European Commission to promote

³⁷ European Investment Bank, "EIB at a glance", [Online]. Available: <https://www.eib.org/en/about/at-a-glance/index.htm>

³⁸ European Commission, "The European Fund for Strategic Investments," [Online]. Available: https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/economy-works-people/european-fund-strategic-investments_en

³⁹ European Investment Bank, "Advisory Services – InnovFin Advisory," [Online]. Available: <https://www.eib.org/en/products/advisory-services/innovfin-advisory/index.htm>

circularity in European cities. In addition to encouraging circular practices, C3 provides advisory services on developing circular economy business models to facilitate access to public funding and investments.⁴⁰

As mentioned above, the EIB provides not only financial support but also advisory services to help improve the financial viability of circular economy. A large number of projects in many different sectors have benefited from these investments, with a total financing agreement of €65.15 billion in 2022⁴¹. The results for the period 2015-2019, broken down by sector, are as follows⁴²:

Sector	Lending (€ millions)	Share
Industry and services	747	30%
Waste management	594	24%
Agriculture and bioeconomy	438	18%
Water management	426	17%
Mobility	95	4%
Urban development	80	3%
Energy	71	3%
Total	2,452	100%

Table 2: EIB Circular Economy Signed Operations, 2015-2019

The EIB Group claims to be constantly adapting to new opportunities, and emerging market needs while working with SMEs to support them to develop new financing projects. One key initiative, InnovFin Advisory coordinated the launch of the European Circular Bioeconomy Fund (ECBF), a venture fund designed to support growth companies with a focus on the circular economy and high innovation potential. The goal of this fund is to help these companies contribute to Europe's environmental goals by 2050.

With a budget of €300 million, the ECBF invest in companies across various sectors, including the blue economy and fisheries, agri-food, industrial biotechnology, biotech

⁴⁰ European Investment Bank, *The Circular City Centre - C3*. [Online]. Available: <https://advisory.eib.org/about/circular-city-centre>

⁴¹ European Investment Bank, "The EIB Group in Numbers," [Online]. Available: <https://www.eib.org/en/about/key-figures/index.htm>

⁴² European Investment Bank, *The EIB in the Circular Economy Guide, 2020*. [Online]. Available: <https://www.eib.org/en/publications/the-eib-in-the-circular-economy-guide>

chemicals and materials, packaging, and household and personal care products⁴³. The EIB provides both financing and advisory services primarily through InnovFin Advisory and the European Investment Advisory Hub (EIAH).

3.2.3 Joint Initiative on Circular Economy

Given the importance of the circular economy in combating climate change and the various programmes designed to help businesses achieve the agreed targets, the Joint Initiative on the Circular Economy (JICE) brought together the EIB and five European promotional banks: Bank Gospodarstwa Krajowego (BGK – Poland), the Caisse des Dépôts Groupe (CDC – France) including Bpifrance and Banque des Territoires, Cassa Depositi e Prestiti (CDP – Italy), the European Investment Bank (EIB), Instituto de Crédito Oficial (ICO – Spain) and KfW – Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau (Germany). In its initial five-year plan (2019-2023), the aim was to accelerate the transition to a circular economy by providing up to €10 billion in loans, financing, technical assistance and guarantees for appropriate circular economy projects by 2023.⁴⁴

The positive impact of this plan is evident when you consider that at the end of the plan, the amount spent on financing the circular economy exceeded the original budget of €10 billion and reached €11.6 billion. For this reason, the plan was extended until 2025 by adding Invest NL as a new member and making an investment commitment of up to €16 billion.⁴⁵

This joint initiative aims to support projects that accelerate the transition to a circular economy over a period of five years. To be eligible for funding, projects must be submitted to one of the partners listed above.

⁴³ ECBF, "Investment Focus," [Online]. Available: <https://www.ecbf.vc/investment-focus>

⁴⁴ European Investment Bank, "EUR 10 Billion to Support the Circular Economy in the EU," 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.eib.org/en/press/all/2019-191-eur-10-billion-to-support-the-circular-economy-in-the-eu>

⁴⁵ European Investment Bank, "The Joint Initiative on Circular Economy (JICE) steps up its commitment to provide €16 billion to circular projects by 2025 and welcomes Invest-NL as new member," Apr. 17, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.eib.org/en/press/all/2024-151-the-joint-initiative-on-circular-economy-jice-steps-up-its-commitment-to-provide-eur16-billion-to-circular-projects-by-2025-and-welcomes-invest-nl-as-new-member>

The sectors that the JICE supports are diverse and include several companies and projects on different topics such as water and waste management, design of innovative materials or the fashion and food industry. For example, Star meat, a Polish company that deals with food waste from meat, or Aquaservice, a Spanish water services company that deals with recycling and repairs, have been supported by this initiative.

3.2.4 European Bank for Reconstruction and Development

The last financial institution to be mentioned at European level is the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD). The EBRD, as well as the rest of the Multilateral Development Banks (MDB) has acknowledged the relevance of the circular economy in the transition to a sustainable economy and in achieving the goals of the Paris Agreement.⁴⁶ More specifically, the EBRD recognizes that financing circular economy projects is a “key” component of the Green Economy transition.⁴⁷ Founded to support the reconstruction of Central and Eastern Europe after the Cold War, the EBRD is committed to promoting market-oriented economies and fostering private sector and entrepreneurial initiatives, with a clear focus on achieving sustainability and circularity.

The EBRD also offers direct financing for SMEs adopting circular economy business models offering customized financial solutions. Investment amounts range from €1 million to €25 million, with an average of €3.5 million, are available in all EBRD-operating countries. This support is tailored to fast-growing local companies looking to improve their competitiveness and corporate governance. However, the EBRD has stipulated that it will not finance projects that do not meet its environmental standards or that may at any time be harmful to the environment or society.⁴⁸ As a result, circular economy business models align well with the bank’s financing priorities.

⁴⁶ European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, “MDBs publish shared vision for circular economy finance at WCEF 2024,” Apr. 19, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ebrd.com/news/2024/mdbs-publish-shared-vision-for-circular-economy-finance-at-wcef-2024.html>

⁴⁷ Ibid.

⁴⁸ European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, “EBRD project financing.” [Online]. Available: <https://www.ebrd.com/work-with-us/project-finance/funding-adviser.html>

In addition to the financing aspect, the EBRD also offers advisory support, connecting businesses with local and international consultants to help them adopt best practices, develop new products, and improve energy and resource efficiency.

Additionally, in 2021, the EBRD launched its first circular economy plan, the Circular Economy Regional Initiative for Turkey and the Western Balkans. This initiative is designed to remove barriers to circular economy adoption, with a focus on SMEs. Funding for the initiative is supported by the Global Environment Facility (GEF) and the technical co-operation of the Austrian Federal Ministry of Finance in the amount of \$13.76 million and \$1 million respectively.⁴⁹

3.3 International Private Investments and other Private Funding Opportunities

Projects aimed at supporting, promoting and participating in the circular economy can be funded by various international actors. While it is true that public funding from European institutions is fundamental for the financing of projects focussing on the circular economy, there is also an increasing interest from private actors. Therefore, there is a growing number of funding opportunities for start-ups and SMEs, which undoubtedly needs to be considered. This section will explore how private financing for circular economy projects operates on an international level.

3.3.1 Asset Management Firms

The transition to a circular economy, which contributes to business prosperity as well as controlling environmental impacts, offers new and better investment opportunities for all sectors. According to the Ellen McArthur Foundation, a circular economy could improve job quality, increase employment and boost Europe's economy by up to €1.8 trillion per year.⁵⁰ For these reasons, asset management firms are increasingly attracted to the new

⁴⁹ EBRD, "EBRD launches first circular-economy programme," [Online]. Available: <https://www.ebrd.com/news/2021/ebd-launches-first-circulareconomy-programme.html>

⁵⁰ Ellen MacArthur Foundation, "Financing the circular economy," [Online]. Available: <https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/topics/finance/overview>

opportunities offered by the circular economy model, both for their contribution to the transition to a carbon-neutral economy and for the benefits of maintaining a strong, sustainable portfolio that enhances their reputation. While most international asset management funds currently focus on financing the circular economy initiatives, providing a comprehensive overview of their strategies would be beyond the scope of this report. Therefore, this section highlights only a selection of the strategies presented by the main asset management companies.

Firstly, the financing of the circular economy should be introduced by the largest asset management fund. For example, the North American company Blackrock, which follows the approach explained previously, sees the circular economy not only as a solution to the climate crisis, but also as a very profitable area for investment.⁵¹ With this in mind, this company has a special fund, the “Circular Economy Fund”, which invests 80% of its assets in circular economy projects. The areas of the circular economy in which this fund can invest are very broad, as it invests in “companies worldwide that benefit from or contribute to the promotion of the circular economy”. In order to decide which companies to invest in, an assessment is made of their ability to manage risk and their growth opportunities.⁵²

Some other asset management companies, such as the Vanguard Group or Fidelity Investments, do not have a dedicated circular investment fund, but are nonetheless committed to sustainability. Therefore, they classify their investments as “sustainable investments”, guaranteeing that their decisions are always guided by sustainability principles. Taking this into account, these companies can demonstrate a commitment to the circular economy, which undoubtedly offers financing opportunities.⁵³

⁵¹ Financial Times, “Funds.” [Online]. Available: <https://markets.ft.com/data/funds/tearsheet/summary?s=LU2041044095:USD>

⁵² BlackRock, “BlackRock Circular Economy Fund.” [Online]. Available: <https://www.blackrock.com/ch/individual/en/products/310165/blackrock-circular-economy-fund>

⁵³ Fidelity International, “Sustainability at Fidelity.” [Online]. Available: <https://www.fidelity.no/sustainable-investing/sustainability-at-fidelity>

3.3.2 Investment Funds

It is worth noting the increasing number of medium-sized funds focussing on investing in circular economy initiatives. Even if their investment capacities are smaller than those of the giant asset management companies mentioned above, they still represent a very interesting way to raise funds. This category includes various investment funds whose business model are based exclusively on investing in projects and initiatives related to the circular economy. In other words, these investment funds are dedicated to researching and investing in new companies related to the circular economy with the aim of increasing their market value and providing them with economic returns in the future.

Although this business model is relatively new, the increasing prominence that the circular economy has gained in political and economic debates has led to the creation of several investment funds specifically focussed on this sector over the last decade. Given that this represents another way to raise funds for circular economy initiatives, it is useful to examine some of these investment funds, how they work and their approach.

One example of this type of investment fund is “Circularity Capital”. This investment fund presents itself as a “a specialist investor in businesses enabling the circular economy”. Their approach is highly specialised and focuses on providing both financial and technical support for the growth of the business model of the companies they want to invest in. To receive their investment, businesses need to engage with them directly and present an innovative business model that either offers an alternative to traditional linear businesses or manufactures or produces materials or products using circular principles. They also focus on financing companies that want to develop technological solutions to facilitate the transition to a circular economy.⁵⁴

Another example of this type of fund is the Circular Innovation Fund. This venture capital fund also focuses on financing circular innovation projects and is active in various regions of the world, including Europe. With a clear focus on mitigating climate change and

⁵⁴ Circularity Capital, “Versnelde Groei & Innovatie in de Circulaire Economie.” [Online]. Available: <https://circularitycapital.com/our-approach>

promoting green growth, this company offers investments for growth-stage companies. The fund targets companies involved in various aspects of the circular economy, such as initiatives in waste management, circular packaging, recycling or innovation.⁵⁵

Lastly, a fund whose investments are directly focussed on the circular economy is known as “Circulate Capital”. This fund’s main unique feature is that it is narrower in terms of the areas of the circular economy it focuses on. Originally focused on reducing plastic waste in the oceans, it has recently broadened its objectives to focus on financing projects that aim to reduce plastic waste in general. Therefore, its main interest is in companies involved in supply chains where plastics are present, not only through capital investment, but also by providing technical expertise.⁵⁶

Even though there are some other investment funds that focus on the circular economy, there is only a limited amount that focus exclusively on financing projects on this topic. Given the increasing importance of the circular economy in the public debate, it is very likely that a growing number of investment funds will attach importance to this topic.

3.3.3 Crowdfunding

A concept that has gained traction recently and has proven a legitimate way to collect the necessary funds for an initiative, project, or product, is crowdfunding. It consists of the product’s owner, who digitally promotes it in the crowdfunding platform, in order to find people willing to provide the financial resources needed to realise the owner’s product. Due to the fact that it is a relatively new funding strategy, no formal institutions are involved in the process yet, therefore it is considered an alternative form of financing.

The main difference between crowdfunding and other traditional funding strategies is the number of contributors and the scale of their contributions. Where traditional funding comes from a small number of sources in sizeable amounts, crowdfunding engages numerous

⁵⁵ Circular Innovation Fund. [Online]. Available: <https://circularinnovationfund.com/>

⁵⁶ Circulate Capital, “A platform for impact and returns.” [Online]. Available: <https://www.circulatecapital.com/impact/>

sources in smaller contributions. Thus, crowdfunding can mostly or entirely fund small initiatives but will only constitute a part of the capital in case of larger projects.

Crowdfunding offers the advantage of serving not only as a funding mechanism but also as a mean of promotion and awareness-building for the initiative in question. By leveraging the broader reach that crowdfunding platforms can offer, projects can attract a large audience whose contributions also serve as a form of validation. If a project quickly meets its funding goal, it can further demonstrate its market potential.

However, despite the possibility that financial institutions may be willing to invest in the project, crowdfunding still presents the setback that, due to its lack of regulation, it can be seen as non-reliable by institutionalised funders.

Crowdfunding can take different forms. One common type is peer-to-peer tending, where a crowdfunding campaign is posted online, and different contributors provide their donations to support the project. Another approach is reward-based, in which the owner of the product or service sets up different “rewards” depending on the funder’s contribution. For example, a tier system can be set up and the funders will receive from the most basic to the most elaborate version of the product they funded). Finally, crowdfunding may be equity-based, where funders will receive the amount, they contributed to company shares.

It is widely accepted that crowdfunding can deliver a business with more than just money to invest. In a study focused on reward-based crowdfunding Leone et al. showed that it can also be a source of some non-monetary benefits such as validation of the business idea, definition of the product/service (through customer feedback), product promotion, innovation, or identification of internationalisation opportunity among others. Furthermore, this type of crowdfunding shapes circular business models in informational mechanisms, innovation networking and marketing aspects – and it can reduce risks connected to the circular business model.⁵⁷

⁵⁷ D. Leone, M. C. Pietronudo, H. Gabteni, and C. Rosaria, “Reward-based crowdfunding for building a valuable circular business model,” *J. Bus. Res.*, vol. 157, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.113562>

Multiple crowdfunding platforms are widely available and well-known to the public, including Kickstarter, GoFundMe and Indiegogo. Additionally, platforms such as LiTA, Invesdor or StartSomeGood provide further crowdfunding opportunities. Beyond these, the European Crowdfunding Network offers professional training and transparent digital financing options.⁵⁸

A success case of circular business model foundation through crowdfunding (kickstarter platform) is Vesica Piscis, a small enterprise created in Elx, Spain, and mainly specialised in footwear. Their business model is based on circular economy and respect to the environment. Their campaign was launched at the beginning of December 2015, using rewards as pairs of shoes, and aiming to obtain €15.000 in one year. In June 2016, the project reached €17.589 allowing them to launch the creation of their business.⁵⁹

⁵⁸ Eurocrowd, "Home," [Online]. Available: <https://eurocrowd.org>

⁵⁹ D. Leone, M. C. Pietronudo, H. Gabteni, and C. Rosaria, "Reward-based crowdfunding for building a valuable circular business model," *J. Bus. Res.*, vol. 157, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.113562>

4 Green Public Procurement

Green Public Procurement (GPP) is defined as “a process whereby public authorities seek to procure goods, services and works that have a lower environmental impact throughout their life cycle than goods, services and works with the same primary function that would otherwise be procured”.⁶⁰ GPP is a valuable tool for advancing the circular economy, as it allows the public sector to leverage its substantial purchasing power – approximately €2 trillion per year (around 14% of the EU’s gross domestic product) – to drive demand for more sustainable products and services. By prioritizing greener procurement choices, public authorities can influence markets, encouraging businesses to adopt circular strategies and more resource-efficient production models.⁶¹

GPP has the potential to reshape markets by stimulating demand for circular solutions. When public authorities integrate sustainability criteria into their procurement processes, industries are incentivized to develop and invest in greener products, services, and technologies.⁶² This shift not only drives innovation but also encourages private sector actors to align their business models with circular economy principles.⁶³ Due to the nature of public procurement processes covering key sectors such as transport, construction, health services, education, GPP can also have a great infrastructural impact, reinforcing sustainability across multiple industries. However, GPP remains a voluntary initiative and public authorities can choose to what extent they implement it. Therefore, considering the impact that public procurement has on the economy, it is evident that a public procurement plan based on promoting sustainability can have a direct impact on the transition to circular economy. However, there are still barriers to further introduce GPP, such as a lack of political support, the perception that green products are more costly, lack of consistent

⁶⁰ European Union, “Green Public Procurement,” [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/what_en.htm

⁶¹ European Union, “Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions Public procurement for a better environment.” [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52008DC0400>

⁶² Ibid.

⁶³ World Bank, “Squaring the Circle: Policies from Europe’s Circular Economy Transition,” Dec. 6, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/region/eca/publication/squaring-circle-europe-circular-economy-transition>

criteria evaluating which products are more environmentally friendly, and the low co-operation between public authorities or the lack of training of staff responsible.⁶⁴

Nowadays, most European Countries (Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain and Sweden) have adopted National Action Plans for GPP, aligning their implementation strategies with the EU Public Procurement Directive 2014/24/EU. As of June 2024, Romania is the only country that does not have a national action plan in force, although efforts are underway to develop one.⁶⁵

In Spain, GPP is regulated by Article 202 of Law 9/2017, of November 8, on Public Sector Contracts. In line with this, the Murcia regional development agency, INFO Murcia, includes environmental and sustainability-related conditions in its procurement specifications and contracts whenever its link with the object of the contract is possible. These requirements apply to various contracts, such as some furniture supply for participation in fairs, travel agency service contracts, audit service contracts, consultancy contracts, IT support service contracts, etc. Failure to comply with these conditions may entail for the contractor the penalties established in the specific administrative clauses that govern that range of contracts.

The European Commission has developed GPP criteria for specific sectors to facilitate the inclusion of environmentally friendly requirements. GPP criteria are to be understood as part of the procurement process and must comply with its standard format and rules as set out in the Public Procurement Directive 2014/24/EU (public works, supply and service contracts). Therefore, following the principles of the European Union's Internal Market, the EU GPP criteria must comply with the following principles: Free movement of goods and services, freedom of establishment; non-discrimination and equal treatment; transparency; proportionality and mutual recognition.

⁶⁴ OECD, "Public Procurement." [Online]. Available: https://www.oecd.org/gov/public-procurement/Going_Green_Best_Practices_for_Sustainable_Procurement.pdf

⁶⁵ European Union, "Green Public Procurement Advisory Group & National Action Plans," *Online*. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/action_plan_en.htm

Apart from the aforementioned criteria, there are some recommendations provided by the EU for some specific sectors. These criteria are not binding, and should be considered as recommendations for public authorities, for them to have more knowledge regarding the level of environmental safety of the products they are purchasing. These specific sectors are the following:

- Cleaning products and services,
- Computers, monitors, tablets and smartphones,
- Data centres, server rooms and cloud services,
- Electricity,
- Food catering services and vending machines,
- Furniture,
- Imaging Equipment, consumables, and print services,
- Office building design,
- Construction and management,
- Paints, varnishes and road markings,
- Public Space Maintenance,
- Road Design, Construction and Maintenance,
- Road lighting and traffic signals,
- Textiles,
- Road transport

The EU's approach to sustainable procurement is further reinforced using "Ecolabels", which plays a crucial role in verifying the environmental impact of products and services. According to the EU directive 2014/24, public contractors may ask for a specific label that proves that the services, works, or supplies that they are purchasing comply with certain environmental requirements.⁶⁶ "Ecolabels" not only simplify decision-making process for procurement officers but also provide businesses with a valuable opportunity to improve their positioning in the European market. By certifying environmental excellence, ecolabels enhance

⁶⁶ European Union, *Directive 2014/24/EU of The European Parliament and of The Council of 26 February 2014 on Public Procurement and Repealing Directive 2004/18/EC*. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014L0024>

transparency, allowing companies to communicate their sustainability credentials effectively and align with the growing demand for green products in public procurement.

5 Public Financing Schemes in the Region of Murcia

In this section, specific public financing schemes in the Region of Murcia are described, including grant programmes from the regional governmental administration (CARM) and the regional development agency (INFO).

5.1 INFO

The main objective of INFO (*Instituto de Fomento de la Región de Murcia*) is to promote regional economic growth and competitiveness in the Region of Murcia by stimulating investment, supporting innovation, and creating an enabling environment for SMEs. In recent years, INFO has increasingly aligned its funding priorities with sustainability and circular economy goals, offering targeted support schemes that foster energy efficiency, carbon footprint reduction, eco-innovation, and sustainable R&D. These funding lines not only enhance the competitiveness of regional enterprises but also contribute to broader environmental objectives by incentivising circular practices across sectors. This section presents an overview of key financial support programmes managed by INFO, including both ongoing and past calls, with data on participation, implementation, and budget allocation.

5.1.1 Grant programme for energy efficiency actions in SMEs and large companies in the industrial sector⁶⁷

The objective of this programme is helping the industrial sector in the incorporation of energy efficient technology and the implementation of control systems. Industry is an intensive sector in energy consumption and, therefore, the efficient and optimised use of such energy is a major factor of competitiveness, so that actions aimed at improving energy efficiency have a very important impact on such competitiveness.

⁶⁷ Instituto Fomento Murcia, "Eficiencia Energética," [Online]. Available: <https://www.institutofomentomurcia.es/web/portal/eficiencia-energetica>

Even though companies have already been making numerous investment efforts in energy matters, there is still a large margin for reducing final energy consumption and carbon dioxide emissions. In that sense, the incorporation of the best available technologies in equipment and processes and the implementation of energy management systems are the two basic mechanisms for improving energy efficiency.

To this end, the Ministry of Industry, Trade and Tourism published Royal Decree 263/2019, of 12 April, which regulates the grant programme with multi-regional ERDF means for energy efficiency actions in SMEs and large companies in the industrial sector. This decree established a mechanism of direct concession to the different Autonomous Communities and called for the publication of an order regulating the grants for the industrial sector.

Four calls have been made in the Region of Murcia since the region was entrusted by IDAE (*Instituto para la Diversificación y Ahorro de la Energía*) to manage the multi-regional ERDF means for grants to SMEs and large companies in energy efficiency. Moreover, among the 161 dossiers presented by industrial companies in the Region of Murcia, 102 dossiers have been approved with a subsidy of €15,03 million, 48% of the grant going to SMEs and the remaining 52% to large companies.

As far as the available budget is concerned, 76% was endorsed to large companies, the other 24% to SMEs. Large firms submitted investments for more amount than SMEs, so the grant endorsed to large investments was superior to SME investments.⁶⁸

5.1.2 HSOS grant line for the calculation and certification of carbon footprint in organisation/product and water footprint⁶⁹

This programme is aimed at encouraging and promoting innovative measures of companies through their climate responsibility and sustainability, looking to improve the competitive

⁶⁸ Instituto Fomento Murcia, “Ayudas INFO para actuaciones de eficiencia energética en PYME y gran empresa del sector industrial.” [Online]. Available: <https://sede.institutofomentomurcia.es/infodirecto/servlet/Controlador?idServicio=1147>

⁶⁹ Instituto Fomento Murcia, “Sostenibilidad Empresarial,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.institutofomentomurcia.es/web/portal/sostenibilidadempresarial>

position of companies and promote business innovation in two types of corporate social responsibility measures: the calculation of the carbon footprint of organisations and products as well as the water footprint of companies.

SMEs may be beneficiaries of the grants contemplated in this programme, and the types of eligible services for the promotion of business innovation through corporate responsibility and climate sustainability are the following: Organisational and product carbon footprint (ISO 14064 and 14067), corporate water footprint (ISO 14046), two open calls in 2022 with 180 SME applicants and grants endorsed for €200,000, and lastly, one open call in 2024 with 58 applicant SMEs for grants endorsed for a budget of €120.000.⁷⁰

5.1.3 Innovation voucher for optimising industrial processes and products eco-innovation⁷¹

The aim of this programme is encouraging and promoting both product design and process improvement for boosting sustainability in regional enterprises, with the final objective to improve the competitive position of companies and promote business innovation. The programme is directed to SMEs located in the Region of Murcia, for either the optimisation of industrial processes or product design (eco-innovation).

One call opened in 2021 with 19 SME applicants, from where a total of 9 SMEs were financed with a total budget of €81,000. Another call opened in 2019 with 41 SME applicants and in this case, a total of 19 SMEs were financed with a total budget of €167,000. Two calls opened in 2023: one with €300,000 that financed 18 projects, and another one that opened in 2023 with €130,000, which financed 21 projects. In 2024, an additional call opened, with €1,400,000 that financed 159 projects.

⁷⁰ Instituto Fomento Murcia, "Cheque de Innovación," [Online]. Available: <https://www.institutofomentomurcia.es/cheques-de-innovacion>

⁷¹ Instituto Fomento Murcia, "Sostenibilidad Empresarial," [Online]. Available: <https://www.institutofomentomurcia.es/web/portal/sostenibilidadempresarial>

5.1.4 R&D support to regional technological centres for developing sustainable products and processes⁷²

The present programme searches to encourage and promoting non-economic research and technological development of products and processes, including knowledge and technology transfer to enterprises, so as to improve the competitive position of companies and promote business innovation. It is thought for technology centres located in the Region of Murcia for services of non-economic research & technological development and knowledge and technology activities for wide dissemination of R&D results.

One call opened in 2022 aimed at 9 technological centre applicants with a total budget of €4,4 million that financed 46 projects. Another call opened in 2023 (for years 2023+2024) aimed at 9 technological centre applicants with a total budget of €9 million that financed 38 projects. Finally, one call opened in 2024 (for years 2025+2026) aimed at 9 technological centre applicants with a total budget of €9 million that financed 36 projects.

5.1.5 R&D support to enterprises for developing sustainable products and processes⁷³

This programme seeks to encouraging and promoting research and technological development of products and processes, with a final aim to improve the competitive position of companies and promote business innovation. It is directed to enterprises located in the Region of Murcia that want to invest in research & technological development.

One call opened in 2020 with a total budget of €6,000,000 that financed 53 projects. Another call opened in 2024 with a total budget of €5,000,000 that financed 68 projects.

5.2. CARM

The CARM, through its various departments and in alignment with the EU's Green Deal and Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), plays a key role in promoting the transition toward a

⁷² Instituto Fomento Murcia, "Home," [Online]. Available: <https://www.institutofomentomurcia.es>

⁷³ Ibid.

circular and climate-resilient economy. By supporting investments that foster innovation, sustainable land use, water reuse, decarbonisation, and rural development, CARM encourages agri-food systems and rural enterprises to adopt more resource-efficient, regenerative, and resilient practices. This section outlines the principal public funding instruments managed or co-funded by CARM that contribute to the implementation of circular economy principles across agriculture, food systems, and rural infrastructure in the region.

5.2.1 Subsidies to operational funds of fruit and vegetable producer organisations (FVPOs)

The purpose of these subsidies is to establish the rules governing the programmes and operational funds of fruit and vegetable producer organisations based in the Region of Murcia. The beneficiaries of this aid will be legal entities and/or companies which have qualified as fruit and vegetable producer organisations and their associations. The aid will be 100% financed by the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF), with an intensity of 50% of the eligible expenditure.

This programme is also extensively regulated at national and Community level. On the one hand, in Spain, Royal Decree 857/2022 establishes the rules governing the operational funds and programmes of producer organisations in the fruit and vegetable sector and their associations, all within the framework of the European Common Agricultural Policy. This decree is complemented by the Order of the Regional Ministry of Water, Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries, which establishes the system of financial aid modalities for eligible costs in the approval of programmes and funds for agricultural producers of fruit and vegetables.

On the other hand, the European Union, in its regulations 2021/2115 and 2021/2116, establishes the guidelines to be followed by the member states for the adoption of strategic plans of the CAP, and for the financing, management and monitoring of the same. This Community legislation is supplemented by delegated regulations 2022/126, 2022/2513 and 2022/2092, as well as by implementing regulation 2022/1863 on market withdrawals for the free distribution of fruit and vegetables.

5.2.2 Establishment and operation of Innovation and Environmental Adaptation (IEA) Task Forces

The objective of this intervention is to support the preparation and/or implementation of one or more innovative projects by an Agri European Innovation Partnership (IAP) Operational Group (GO) to accelerate innovation in the agri-food and forestry sector and to respond to the modernisation needs of the primary sector by promoting knowledge sharing, innovation and digitisation of agriculture and rural areas, and to promote the adoption of these approaches in their activity. The GOs are aimed at the productivity and sustainability of the agri-food and forestry sector, focusing on the productive link as a lever for change towards the green and digital transition of both the primary sector and rural areas. In relation to the beneficiaries, those natural or legal persons, including public administrations, that form part of an AEI-Agri Operational Group, constituted for the preparation and/or implementation of one or more projects aimed at the modernisation of the agri-food and forestry sector, or operational groups constituted as a legal entity, will be eligible for support. The sources of funding will be 28% from the CARM, 60% from the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and 12% from the MA, with an intensity of 100% of the eligible expenses, up to a maximum of 100,000€ per application.

This intervention is regulated by the Order of 31 July 2024 of the Regional Ministry of Water, Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries, which establishes the regulatory bases for the granting of subsidies for cooperation for the preparation and implementation of innovation projects carried out by the operational groups of the AEI.

5.1.6 Subsidies for investments in agricultural holdings

The objective of these subsidies is to grant aid, on a competitive basis, to cover part of the eligible investments in agricultural holdings located in the Region of Murcia, established in the Spanish PEPAC (period 2023-2027) as interventions 6841.1 (Productive investments in agricultural holdings linked to contributing to the mitigation-adaptation to climate change, efficient use of natural resources and animal welfare) and 6841.2 (Investments in modernisation and/or improvement of agricultural holdings). The beneficiaries of this aid are citizens, companies and other entities, as well as the owners of agricultural holdings that make investments in their holdings. The financing comes 60% from the EAFRD, 28% from

CARM and 12% from MARM, the intensity of which is 40% of the eligible amount of the eligible investments in general and may be increased by a further 40%.

These aids are regulated at national level, on the one hand, by Law 30/2022, and on the other hand, by the Order of 12 April 2024 of the Regional Ministry of Water, Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries, which establishes the regulatory bases for aid for investment in agricultural holdings, in the framework of the Strategic Plan of the Common Agricultural Policy.

5.1.7 Aid for the creation of agricultural enterprises by young farmers

The objective of this subsidies is to attract and support young farmers, as well as to facilitate sustainable business development in rural areas. It also aims to promote employment, growth, gender equality, including women's participation in agriculture, social inclusion and local development in rural areas, including the circular bio-economy and sustainable forestry. Therefore, the grants are aimed at young citizens, 60% of which are financed by the EAFRD, 28% by CARM and 12% by MARM. The amount of the aid will be 27,500 euros (basic module) per young person installed, which may be increased up to a maximum of 67,000 euros per young person. This aid is regulated by the Order of 14 March 2023, of the Regional Ministry of Water, Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries, which establishes the regulatory bases for the same.

5.1.8 Grants for investment in processing, marketing and development of agricultural products

These aids seek to grant aid for investments in the transformation, marketing and development of agri-food products, increasing yield and economic development, promoting quality products, improving food safety, promoting innovation and digital transformation, the development of new products and the valorisation of by-products and improving social and economic sustainability ratios with a positive impact on the rural environment of the Region of Murcia. The beneficiaries will be those food industries with physical or legal personality and communities of goods whose work centres are located in the Region of Murcia.

As regards the sources of financing, 60% of the amount will be provided by the EAFRD; 12% by the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAPA), charged to the General State Budget, and 28% by the Regional Ministry of Water, Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries. The aid will consist of 25% in general for SMEs, 20% for products outside Annex I of the EU Treaty and, in mountain areas, an additional 5%. However, in the case of large companies, the aid will be 18%.

These aids are regulated by the Order of 5 April 2024 of the Regional Ministry of Water, Agriculture and Livestock, as well as by an extract of the Order of 16 April 2024 of the Regional Ministry of Water, Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries by which aid for investments in processing, marketing and/or development of agri-food products of the Strategic Plan of the Common Agricultural Policy is called for the year 2024.

5.1.9 Grants for the consolidation of irrigation by using reclaimed water from wastewater reservoirs

These aids seek to consolidate pre-existing irrigation systems in irrigation communities through the execution of new works, installations, devices and equipment that allow the incorporation and use in irrigation areas of reclaimed water from wastewater treatment plants. Companies and other entities may benefit from this aid, with 63% of the amount coming from the EAFRD, 11% from the MARM and 26% from the CARM.

On the other hand, an aid intensity of 40% of the eligible investment budget is established, except for investments in renewable energies, where the intensity will be 20%. In any case, the maximum amount of aid will not exceed EUR 400,000 per application. These subsidies are regulated by means of the Order of 24 May 2019, of the Regional Ministry of Water, Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries.

5.1.10 Grant for the improvement of energy efficiency and renewable energy generation in irrigation communities. RDP 2014-2022 / IRUE Funds. Call for proposals 2024

This call for applications is aimed at improving energy efficiency and the generation of renewable energy in irrigation communities and irrigation communities in general in the

Region of Murcia. The beneficiaries of this aid are companies and other entities, as well as what are known as irrigation communities and general irrigation communities (user communities regulated in Chapter IV of the Consolidated Text of the Water Act approved by Royal Legislative Decree 1/2001 of 20 July 2001 and in Chapter IV of the Regulations on the Public Hydraulic Domain approved by Royal Decree 849/1986 of 11 April 1986). The financing of the aid comes from the European Union Recovery Instrument (EURI) funds, with an intensity of 40% of the eligible investment budget, up to a maximum aid amount of 850,000 euros per application.

This type of aid is regulated, on the one hand, by the extract of the Order of 16 May 2024 of the Regional Ministry of Water, Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries, responsible for approving the call for this aid, and on the other hand, by the Order of 22 May 2020 of the Regional Ministry of Water, Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries and the Environment, which establishes the regulatory bases for the aid.

6 Private Financing Schemes in the Region of Murcia

Private financing plays a crucial role in driving the growth and development of circular economy initiatives. By providing essential capital, expertise, and networks, private funding enables businesses to scale, innovate, and advance their sustainability goals.

The optimal financing mechanism for a circular economy project depends on its development stage and unique business model. Early-stage ventures may rely on angel investors or venture capital firms, while more established companies might seek funding from private equity funds or institutional investors.

The following sections outline the key private financing options available for circular economy initiatives, categorized into two main groups:

1. **Bank and Financial Cooperative Systems:** This section will examine traditional debt financing options, such as loans and green loans, as well as other financial products offered by banks and cooperative banks.
2. **Alternative Private Financing Schemes in the Region of Murcia:** This section will explore a broader spectrum of financing mechanisms, including equity financing, crowdfunding, leasing, and impact investing.

By understanding the nuances of these financing options, circular economy entrepreneurs and project developers can make informed decisions to secure the necessary capital and propel their sustainable ventures forward.

6.1 Bank and Financial Cooperatives Schemes

Traditional banking institutions, including commercial banks and cooperative banks, offer a range of financing mechanisms that can be tailored to the specific needs of circular economy initiatives. These institutions often provide debt-based financing, such as loans and green

loans, as well as other financial products like guarantees and leasing. An overview of the different private financing mechanisms is given on the table below.

Financial Mechanism	Sub-type	Description
Debt	Loans	Traditional debt financing, often secured by collateral. Can be used for various purposes, including working capital, equipment purchases, and facility expansion.
	Green Loans	Loans specifically designed to finance environmentally friendly projects, such as renewable energy, energy efficiency, and waste reduction.
	Bonds	Debt securities issued by banks or corporations to raise capital. While not as common for smaller businesses, some cooperative banks may offer bond issuance services.
	Green Bonds	Bonds specifically issued to finance environmental projects, such as renewable energy, clean transportation, and sustainable agriculture.
Alternative forms of funding	Guarantees	Financial instruments that guarantee repayment of a loan, reducing the risk for lenders and improving access to credit.
	Leasing	A financing arrangement where the bank purchases an asset and leases it to the borrower. This can be particularly useful for financing equipment or vehicles.
Equity	Equity Investments	In some cases, banks, especially development banks, may invest equity in promising circular economy ventures, particularly those with a strong social or environmental impact.

Table 3: Main Bank and Cooperative Bank Financing Mechanisms.

In Spain, the Bank of Spain has demonstrated its commitment to sustainable economy by the analysis of climate change impacts and the transition towards a more sustainable growth model in its research agenda. This is reflected in the last report of analytical and research priorities for 2020-2024⁷⁴. Among the long-term trends of the Spanish economy, it prioritises the study of the informative content on sustainability and the degree of compliance with the recommendations on climate risk included in corporate reports, as well as the incorporation of sustainability factors in public debt markets, in portfolio management and in the conduct of monetary policy.

According to the Regional Statistics Center of Murcia, in 2022, 25 different credit institutions operated in the Region, including credit cooperatives and banks. Together they totalled to 520 branches, from which 187 are based in Murcia city, and 76 in Cartagena, the two most populated cities in the region. The most representative entities among banks are Caixabank, with 167 branches, and Cajamar Group, with 113 branches, within credit cooperatives.

The Cajamar Cooperative Group has consistently focused on local development, with the agri-food sector serving as its primary area of activity. Its commitment lies in supporting the agricultural industry, include both core businesses and auxiliary industries, ensuring long-term sectoral growth and sustainability.

Over the years, Cajamar's trajectory has closely aligned with the economic development of the regions where it operates. Through its engagement, it has integrated agri-food sector values into its corporate identity, recognising the sector as a strategic pillar of its operations. Given that the agri-food industry represents a significant portion of its total activity, Cajamar has established a dedicated internal and external structure to support its role in fostering sectoral resilience and development. Cajamar has developed a distinct approach to supporting the agri-food sector, setting it apart within the financial landscape:

- A wide range of specific products and services;

⁷⁴ Banco de España, "Prioridades analíticas y de investigación del Banco de España 2020–2024," [Online]. Available: https://www.bde.es/f/webbde/INF/MenuVertical/AnalisisEconomico/Actualizacion_2021_Prioridades_analiticas_BE.pdf

- Its commitment to research and innovation in production systems;
- And the dissemination of knowledge among farmers and managers in the auxiliary industry.

Providing support and quality financial services to farmers and agri-food businesses remains a key priority for Cajamar Cooperative Group, regardless of their size. This commitment extends to cooperatives, which have played a fundamental role in ensuring that the efforts of farmers translate into economic impact, both across Spain and in various European markets.

The Ethics and Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Management Committee of Banco de Crédito Cooperativo, head of Grupo Cooperativo Cajamar, ratifies and promotes its commitment to the social, economic, and sustainable environment in which it interacts. While the group's core activities have a minimal direct environmental impact, its business model integrates sustainable development principles, taking into account not only direct but also indirect impacts—including those arising from its financing activities, asset management, and supply chain operations.

Cajamar Cooperative Group aims to support economic development and social progress by providing financial solutions that serve its members, clients, and the broader community. Its strategy is based on the principles of cooperation, social economy, and sustainable development. It seeks to be the leading cooperative banking institution in Spain and a reference for the agri-food sector, recognized for its financial strength, commitment, and ethical standards in its relationships with customers, members, employees, and the environment. Its purpose is to foster well-being and social progress, encouraging innovation and collaboration to strengthen the sustainable development of local and regional economies.

The cooperative banking model brings diversity to the banking system. By focusing on long-term, locally embedded economic development, it fosters sustainable relationships with communities and mitigates risks associated with market speculation and financial bubbles. Additionally, its countercyclical approach helps address key financial challenges, including

moral hazard, adverse selection, and asymmetric information, thereby contributing to a more resilient and transparent financial system. Their main objectives are:

- To adapt to regulatory expectations, which encompass compliance with the EU action plan for sustainable finance and adaptation to important regulatory changes in disclosure and management of environmental risks;
- To expand the products and services catalogue that include ESG criteria (Environmental, Social and Governance), responding to demand of individuals and companies and taking advantage of financing opportunities that will arise in the transition towards low carbon economy;
- To advance in climate and environmental risk management through the implementation of climate indicators in the risk methodology and manuals, and developments in carbonisation analysis process of the portfolio;
- To develop and implement an internal training plan in sustainable finance to strengthen the presence of values related to sustainability in the group's culture.
- Continue reinforcing the presence of sustainability and the consolidation of ESG criteria in the group's strategy and governance.

In 2023, The European Investment Bank (EIB) and Grupo Cooperativo Cajamar signed a purchase agreement of a €350 million covered bond issue. The transaction enables the cooperative bank Cajamar to make up to €784 million in financing available to support investment in projects of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and mid-caps, especially those operating in rural areas, including those with links to the agri-food sector, and up to €196 million to accelerate the green transition.

CaixaBank is another key financial institution in the region. Its environmental and climate strategy aims to support the transition to sustainability through financing and investment in sustainable projects, environmental and climate risk management, and the reduction of the direct impact of its operations. As part of this strategy, CaixaBank offers specific financial lines, including:

- Loans linked to sustainability variables, which are loans linked to ESG criteria (€10,832 million mobilised through the 92 loans made available in 2021);
- Green loans: These are loans with a positive environmental impact, whose underlying are eligible projects or assets, in areas such as renewable energy, energy efficiency, sustainable transport, emission reduction, waste treatment and sustainable building, which comply with the Green Loan Principles (GLP) issued by the Loan Market Association (€1,625 million mobilised in 36 green loans in 2021).
- Eco-financing: Encouraging sustainable investments that use resources more efficiently and/or reduce environmental impacts. This type of financing consists of offering personal eco-loans and eco-microloans to finance the purchase of efficient vehicles and household appliances and home renovations to improve energy efficiency. Eco-financing could also be directed towards projects related to efficient water use, renewable energies, waste management, energy efficiency, ecological agriculture and rural development, through eco-financing lines for the agricultural sector (€61 million available through 919 loans linked to eco-financing lines in 2021).

Banco Sabadell is also among the most represented entities in the region of Murcia. It has promoted different projects related to circular economy (Givers, W3R, Ding Dong project or B-COME). Thus, Banco Sabadell is committed to sustainability, and it has established a framework for action that ensures the integration into a strategy of a forward-looking vision in relation to ESG commitments, that aligns its business objectives with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and that establishes action levers to generate transformation and promotion activities. To do that, it has brought on board all the institution's corporate bodies, establishing four strategic pillars:

- Progress as a sustainable institution;
- Support customers in the transition to a sustainable economy;
- Offer investment opportunities that contribute to sustainability;
- Work together for a sustainable and cohesive society.

Banco Santander is another bank entity which has reinforced its commitment to the circular economy, for example, by converting its cards into street furniture. It has also implemented subsidies and grants for sustainability, such as aids for energy efficiency, self-consumption aid or moves plan.⁷⁵

Among other entities with presence in Murcia, it is also worth mentioning Banco Bilbao Vizcaya Argentaria (BBVA), which presents a wide portfolio of funds for investing in sustainable assets. Other programmes and sustainable financial lines can be consulted on the following websites:

Entity	Link
Bancofar	https://cbnk.es/dam/jcr:66e41523-e872-43cf-b0b4-836a1cd9816f/CBNK Memoria Sostenibilidad 2023.pdf
Bankinter	https://www.bankinter.com/webcorporativa/informacion-corporativa/banca-sostenible/plan-sostenibilidad
BBVA	https://www.bbva.com/es/sostenibilidad/
CaixaBank	https://www.caixabank.com/es/sostenibilidad.html
Caja Rural Central	https://www.ruralcentral.es/es/sostenibilidad
Caja Rural de Granada	https://www.cajaruralgranada.es/es/sostenibilidad
Cajamar	https://www.cajamar.es/es/comun/sostenibilidad/
Deutsche Bank	https://country.db.com/spain/sostenibilidad
Ibercaja	https://www.ibercaja.es/particulares/blog/sostenibilidad/
ING	https://www.ing.es/sobre-ing/banca-responsable/planeta
Kutxabank	https://www.kutxabank.eus/cs/Satellite/kutxabank/es/responsabilidad_social_brempresaria/memoria-de-sostenibilidad
Renta 4	https://www.r4.com/que-necesitas/compromiso-social/inversion-sostenible
Sabadell	https://www.grupbancsabadell.com/corp/es/sostenibilidad/compromiso-sostenible.html

⁷⁵ Banco Santander, "Ayudas y subvenciones verdes," [Online]. Available: <https://www.bancosantander.es/en/santander-sostenible/ayudas-subvenciones-verdes>

Santander <https://www.santander.com/es/stories/-sostenibilidad>

6.2 Alternative Private Financing Schemes in the Region of Murcia

Traditionally banks, institutional investors, and governments have been the main and dominant financing sources in the economic system. It should be noted, however, that also other funding sources and instruments exist. These forms of funding, often labelled as alternative forms of funding, may be interesting for circular economy.

6.2.1. Venture Capital (VC)

Venture capital firms invest in early-stage companies with high growth potential, often providing critical funding to innovative circular economy startups. Murcia Emprende, for example, is a regional venture capital firm that invests in early-stage companies in the Region of Murcia, and who still hold a track record of supporting innovative and sustainable businesses in the region.

6.6.2. Private Equity

Private equity firms invest in established companies, often seeking to improve operations, facilitate acquisitions, or support expansion. They can be a valuable source of capital for mature circular economy businesses.

Equity finance refers to a method of financing where a company raises capital by selling a portion of its ownership to investors. Unlike debt financing, which involves borrowing money and repaying it with interest, equity finance involves exchanging a part of the company's equity for capital. This makes equity finance a non-debt financing option that can be particularly beneficial for startups and small businesses.

Private equity financing is a crucial source of capital for circular economy businesses, particularly during their growth and expansion stages. This table outlines the key sources of equity capital at different stages of a company's life cycle.

Stage in Business Life Cycle	Source of Equity Capital
Start-up	Friends & Family / Angel
Early stage	Angel / Venture Capital
Growth	Venture Capital / Private Equity
Buy-and-Build / M&A	Private Equity
Buyout	Private Equity
Later stage	Private Equity / Listed Equity Markets

Table 4. Sources of Equity Capital and Company's stage of development

While there may not be specific private equity firms exclusively focused on circular economy in Murcia, larger national and international private equity funds might invest in regional companies with strong sustainability profiles.

6.2.3. Crowdfunding

Crowdfunding platforms enable companies to raise capital from a large number of individuals, which can be particularly useful for circular economy projects that resonate with a specific community or target audience. In that sense, international platforms like Kickstarter or Indiegogo can be used by entrepreneurs to raise funds for circular economy projects, especially those with a strong social or environmental impact.

6.2.4. Angel Investors

Angel investors are wealthy individuals who invest their own money in early-stage companies. They can provide crucial seed funding and mentorship to emerging circular economy ventures. **MurciaBan** is a non-profit organization that acts as a network

connecting business angels and entrepreneurs in the Region of Murcia. Its primary objective is to foster a culture of entrepreneurship and innovation, particularly by facilitating access to financing for promising projects. While MurciaBan doesn't explicitly focus on circular economy projects, its general mission of supporting innovative and sustainable businesses aligns well with the principles of the circular economy.

7 Financing Schemes & Agro2Circular Business Models

Food production processes are becoming increasingly intensive in energy, land, and water consumption, posing significant pressure on global planetary boundaries.⁷⁶ In particular, intensive agricultural practices are responsible for one-third of global terrestrial acidification⁷⁷ and 80% of global deforestation.⁷⁸ The agri-food sector is also one of the highest contributors to climate change, releasing between 21 and 37% of total Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions.⁷⁹ In Europe, food production alone is responsible for 30% of GHG emissions.⁸⁰

Beyond emissions, the environmental impact of food production is further exacerbated by high losses across the supply chain, with approximately 20% of globally produced food being produced.⁸¹ Additionally, multilayer plastic films, widely used in industrial food packaging and agricultural applications, present a significant waste management challenge. A low percentage of these plastics are sorted and recycled in Europe.⁸² That phenomenon is explained due to several reasons, including the lack of sorting and recycling technologies and the unavailability of financially and environmentally sustainable models for the valorisation of this type of waste. Most of that waste is indeed landfilled or incinerated, generating a relevant environmental burden and a loss of economic value.

⁷⁶ M. Crippa et al., "Food Systems Are Responsible for a Third of Global Anthropogenic GHG Emissions," *Nature Food*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 198–209, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-021-00225-9>

⁷⁷ J. Poore and T. Nemecek, "Reducing Food's Environmental Impacts through Producers and Consumers," *Science*, vol. 360, no. 6392, pp. 987–992, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aag0216>

⁷⁸ FAO, *Forests and Agriculture: Land-Use Challenges and Opportunities*. State of the World's Forests 2016, 2016.

⁷⁹ IPCC, *Summary for Policymakers: Special Report on Climate Change and Land*, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ipcc.ch/srccl/chapter/summary-for-policymakers/>

⁸⁰ M. Crippa et al., "Food Systems Are Responsible for a Third of Global Anthropogenic GHG Emissions," *Nature Food*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 198–209, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-021-00225-9>

⁸¹ UNEP, *UNEP Food Waste Index Report 2021*, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://www.unep.org/resources/report/unep-food-waste-index-report-2021>

⁸² A.-S. Bauer et al., "Recyclability and Redesign Challenges in Multilayer Flexible Food Packaging: A Review," *Foods*, vol. 10, p. 2702, DOI:[10.3390/foods10112702](https://doi.org/10.3390/foods10112702)

In this context, applying circular economy principles in the agri-food sector constitutes a great opportunity to reduce its environmental impacts and to develop more sustainable food systems, enabling the transition towards resource-efficient production models.⁸³ Shifting from a linear to a circular economy requires not only the adoption of new products, technologies and processes, but also the implementation of innovative business models that create new ways to generate value for both companies and society, contributing to sustainability, efficiency and productivity.⁸⁴ This chapter explores the concept of circular business models within the Agro2Circular project and examines its connection with the financing schemes presented in this deliverable.

A business model generally describes how a firm generates, captures, and delivers value.⁸⁵ It provides a simplified representation of the elements constituting a complex organisational system, the interactions between them, and how they relate to the organisation's business logic.⁸⁶ In other words, a business model represents a firm's competitive strategy.⁸⁷ Circular business models aim to integrate principles of circular economy (reuse, reduce recycle) into the business model design, enabling companies to internalise social and environmental costs of materials and products while optimising the value of resources.⁸⁸

Beyond reducing natural resource consumption, circular business models also differ from traditional business models in their approach across the value chain.⁸⁹ For example, a

⁸³ OECD, *Business Models for the Circular Economy: Opportunities and Challenges for Policy*, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.oecd.org/environment/business-models-for-the-circular-economy-g2g9dd62-en.htm>

⁸⁴ A. Bianchini, J. Rossi, and M. Pellegrini, "Overcoming the Main Barriers of Circular Economy Implementation through a New Visualization Tool for Circular Business Models," *Sustainability*, vol. 11, no. 23, p. 6614, DOI:[10.3390/su11236614](https://doi.org/10.3390/su11236614)

⁸⁵ A. Osterwalder, Y. Pigneur, and C. L. Tucci, "Clarifying Business Models: Origins, Present, and Future of the Concept," *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, vol. 16, DOI:[10.17705/1CAIS.01601](https://doi.org/10.17705/1CAIS.01601)

⁸⁶ M. Geissdoerfer, S. N. Morioka, M. M. de Carvalho, and S. Evans, "Business Models and Supply Chains for the Circular Economy," *J. Clean. Prod.*, vol. 190, pp. 712–721, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.04.159>

⁸⁷ OECD, *Business Models for the Circular Economy: Opportunities and Challenges for Policy*, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.oecd.org/environment/business-models-for-the-circular-economy-g2g9dd62-en.htm>

⁸⁸ A. P. M. Velenturf and P. Purnell, "Principles for a Sustainable Circular Economy," *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, vol. 27, pp. 1437–1457, DOI:[10.1016/j.spc.2021.02.018](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2021.02.018)

⁸⁹ OECD, *Business Models for the Circular Economy: Opportunities and Challenges for Policy*, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.oecd.org/environment/business-models-for-the-circular-economy-g2g9dd62-en.htm>

circular sales strategy prioritizes higher-quality, longer-lasting products over high sales volumes of short-lived goods, which is typical in traditional business models. Another common circular approach focuses on providing access to shared products rather than individual ownership. Additionally, circular businesses often offer repair and remanufacturing services to maximize material value and strengthen customer loyalty.

The growing literature on circular business models provides a great variety of approaches and definitions. Among the existing taxonomies, this chapter adopts the one adopted by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)⁹⁰, which categorises circular activities according to the underlying business proposition. According to the OECD report, there are five major business models: *circular supply models*, *resource recovery models*, *product life extension models*, *sharing models*, and *product service system models*. Figure 3 summarises the key features of the mentioned circular business, while Figure 4 illustrates their impact on the linear economy value chain.

	Circular supply	Resource recovery	Product life extension	Sharing	Product service system
Key characteristic	Replace traditional material inputs with renewable, bio-based, recovered ones	Produce secondary raw materials from waste	Extend product lives	Increase utilisation of existing products and assets	Provision of services rather than products. Product ownership remains with supplier
Resource efficiency driver	Close material loops	Close material loops	Slow material loops	Narrow resource flows	Narrow resource flows
Business model sub-types	Cradle to cradle	Industrial symbiosis	Classic long life	Co-ownership	Product-oriented
		Recycling	Direct reuse	Co-access	User-oriented
		Upcycling	Repair		Result-oriented
		Downcycling	Refurbishment		
Main sectors currently applied in	Diverse consumer product sectors	Metals	Automotive	Short term lodging	Transport
		Paper and pulp	Heavy machinery	Transport	Chemicals
		Plastics	Electronics	Machinery	Energy
				Consumer products	

Table 5: The Impact of Circular Business Models on a Linear Economy (OECD, 2019)

⁹⁰ Ibid.

Table 6: Circular Business Impact on the Linear Economy Value Chain

In the context of Agro2Circular, the circular supply models and resource recovery models are recognized as the most relevant business models for the project.

Circular supply business models differ from linear models by replacing traditional inputs with more sustainable alternatives, such as bio-based, renewable, or recovered materials. By adopting this approach, companies can simultaneously reduce the environmental pressures across their supply chains while ensuring that input materials do not become waste. This strategy also aligns with the resource recovery model, where material recovery is considered early in the process. The advantages of these business models include reduced regulatory risks associated with stricter environmental policies and lower dependency on natural resources concentrated in a limited number of countries. Additionally, by replacing conventional inputs with sustainable alternatives, firms can position their products as 'green', expanding their appeal to environmentally conscious consumers.

To design a circular supply agri-food business, the Ellen MacArthur Foundation suggests selecting inputs and ingredients that meet specific criteria. These include greater diversity, which increases the genetic resilience of crops and livestock; upcycling, which maximizes the return on invested resources such as land and energy; lower environmental impact, for example, by shifting from animal to plant-based proteins; and regenerative production, which incorporates context-specific practices that enhance food output, biodiversity, and climate benefits.⁹¹

⁹¹ Ellen MacArthur Foundation, "The Big Food Redesign," 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/news/the-big-food-redesign-new-study-launched-today>

The core strategy of *resource recovery business models* is to produce secondary raw materials from waste streams. This model includes three different activities, which are generally carried out by different actors: collection, sorting, and secondary production. In most cases, local governments oversee waste collection, while private firms manage secondary production. Sorting can be handled by either public facilities or the private sector. Resource recovery processes take various forms, including downcycling, which produces lower-quality raw materials; upcycling, which generates higher-quality raw materials; and closed-loop recycling (industrial symbiosis), where secondary raw materials become inputs for other manufacturing processes.

In food production, there is growing interest in processing technologies for food waste reuse and recycling.⁹² Among the most effective applications, food waste can be used as fertilisers, reducing the need for synthetic and more expensive alternatives.⁹³ Additional applications include using food waste as compost to nourish the soil, as bioplastic or textile fibres⁹⁴, as biogas, and as animal feed.⁹⁵

To support the development and implementation of circular business models, several visualization tools have been developed, based on the traditional business model canvas. This tool provides a structured approach to mapping how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value and is a key step in business development.⁹⁶ According to Osterwalder, Pigneur, and Tucci (2005), a business model consists of nine elements: value proposition; target customer; distribution channel; relationship with different customer segments; value

⁹² V. Rizos et al., "Barriers and Enablers for Implementing Circular Economy Business Models: Evidence from the Electrical and Electronic Equipment and Agri-Food Value Chains," 2021.

⁹³ UNEP, *UNEP Food Waste Index Report 2021*, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://www.unep.org/resources/report/unep-food-waste-index-report-2021>

⁹⁴ J. Esteban and M. Ladero, "Food Waste as a Source of Value-Added Chemicals and Materials: A Biorefinery Perspective," *Int. J. Food Sci. Technol.*, vol. 53, no. 5, pp. 1095–1108, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijfs.13726>

⁹⁵ K. Murugesan et al., "Chapter Eleven - Conversion of Food Waste to Animal Feeds," in *Curr. Dev. Biotechnol. Bioeng.*, J. Wong et al., Eds., 2021, pp. 305–324. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-819148-4.00011-7>

⁹⁶ A. Osterwalder, Y. Pigneur, and C. L. Tucci, "Clarifying Business Models: Origins, Present, and Future of the Concept," *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, vol. 16, doi: 10.17705/1CAIS.01601.

configuration; core competency; partner network; cost structure; revenue model. The following table summarises these components:

Elements of Business Model	Description
Value proposition	Gives an overall view of a company's bundle of products and services.
Target customer	Describes the segments of customers a company wants to offer value to.
Distribution channel	Describes the various means of the company to get in touch with its customers.
Relationship	Explains the kind of links a company establishes between itself and its different customer segments.
Value configurations	Describes the arrangement of activities and resources.
Core competency	Outlines the competencies necessary to execute the company's business model.
Partner network	Portrays the network of cooperative agreements with other companies necessary to efficiently offer and commercialise value.
Cost structure	Sums up the monetary consequences of the means employed in the business model.
Revenue model	Describes the way a company makes money through a variety of revenue flows.

In the context of circular economy, a set of adaptations of the traditional business model canvas proposed by Osterwalder et al. (2005) have been developed to include social, environmental, and economic aspects.⁹⁷ Circular solutions often generate a set of non-monetary benefits that are difficult to quantify and frequently overlooked.⁹⁸ Integrating these

⁹⁷ A.-T. Braun, O. Schöllhammer, and B. Rosenkranz, "Adaptation of the Business Model Canvas Template to Develop Business Models for the Circular Economy," *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 99, pp. 698–702, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781035301003.00022>

⁹⁸ CCRI, "Methodology for the implementation of a circular economy at the local and regional scale," *European Union, LIFE Programme*. [Online]. Available: https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/life_en

components to the business model canvas allows for a more comprehensive consideration of social and environmental impacts during the business development process.

One example is the canvas developed within the "Route to Circular Economy" project, funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research program. This model expands the traditional nine business model elements by adding two additional components that account for the social and environmental costs and benefits of business activities.⁹⁹ The goal of this adaptation is to highlight the role of sustainability and circularity in creating value for both people and the planet.

Another example is the Ecocanvas, developed by Daou et al. (2020).¹⁰⁰ Unlike the previous model, the Ecocanvas does not focus on business impact, but rather expands the economically driven approach of the original canvas by incorporating external business challenges. These challenges are categorized into legal, environmental, and social factors. Economic and legal challenges may include stricter environmental regulations, such as emission taxes, market innovations, or macroeconomic fluctuations. Environmental challenges encompass issues affecting production and supply chains, such as water scarcity, climate change, and pollution. Social and technological challenges refer to cultural and technological shifts that influence consumer behavior. By integrating these elements, this model enables businesses to identify external drivers of change and take proactive steps to embrace eco-innovation and long-term competitiveness.

Recently, the key drivers guiding the adoption of circular business models have been the intensification of business risks from operating a linear production model (e.g., supply chain stability and new regulations), technological advancements that reduce the cost structure of circular activities, and the shift in consumer preferences toward more sustainable

⁹⁹ S. McDermott, D. Morwood, P. Laczko, R. Slaughter, and A. Smith-Gillespie, *Circular Business Model Innovation Toolkit*, n.d. [Online]. Available: <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5c88a8834&appId=PPGMS>

¹⁰⁰ A. Daou, C. Mallat, G. Chammas, N. Cerantola, S. Kayed, and N. A. Saliba, "The Ecocanvas as a Business Model Canvas for a Circular Economy," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 258, p. 120938, DOI:[10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120938](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120938)

alternatives.¹⁰¹ Despite these forces, in most sectors, the market penetration of the circular business model remains moderate (around 5-10%).¹⁰²

On the other hand, several barriers, both internal and external, influence the adoption and scale-up of circular businesses. According to Bianchini et al. (2019), challenges faced when implementing a circular business model span various areas, including internal processes (e.g., redefining business strategy), technical barriers (e.g., need for specialized expertise), market barriers (e.g., lack of supply network support), institutional, regulatory, and social barriers (e.g., misaligned incentives), and financial and economic barriers (e.g., need for long-term investment and costly management processes).

The authors also highlight that the success of a circular business directly depends on a network of companies working together to close material loops. Since these stakeholders are interdependent but operate independently, an efficient exchange of information and feedback is essential to reduce uncertainties associated with circular business strategies.¹⁰³ Focusing on the agri-food sector, the Centre for European Policy Studies conducted an in-depth analysis by interviewing 41 case-study companies involved in the EU-funded CIRC4Life project to identify the main challenges faced when implementing circular activities. According to the collected results, policy and regulation, along with financial and economic factors, were identified as the most significant obstacles by most of the surveyed companies.

Policy-related barriers refer to difficulties arising from bureaucracy and administrative processes. For instance, obtaining official recognition for a circular process using food production leftovers may involve excessive administrative requirements, discouraging companies from utilizing these inputs. Financial and economic factors mainly concern two aspects: first, implementing more sustainable and circular approaches often entails higher

¹⁰¹ OECD, *Business Models for the Circular Economy: Opportunities and Challenges for Policy*, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.oecd.org/environment/business-models-for-the-circular-economy-g2g9dd62-en.htm> ; I. Uvarova, D. Atstāja, and V. Korpa, "Challenges of the Introduction of Circular Business Models within Rural SMEs of EU," *Economic Studies*, vol. 9, no. 2, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.20472/ES.2020.9.2.008>

¹⁰² OECD, *Business Models for the Circular Economy: Opportunities and Challenges for Policy*, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.oecd.org/environment/business-models-for-the-circular-economy-g2g9dd62-en.htm>

¹⁰³ Ibid.

costs, such as collection and treatment of side streams from food production; second, limited access to financial resources is a major obstacle for agri-food businesses, particularly in their early stages, when additional support is crucial to achieving financial sustainability.

The financial support needed for a circular business varies depending on its development and implementation stage: R&D (pre-revenue), start-up (pre-profit), scale-up (pre-profit to profit), growth (profit), and maturity (stable income). Analysing the business and financial model of a circular solution is a useful approach to determining its funding and financing needs across these stages.¹⁰⁴

A business and financial analysis involve identifying the relevant costs and expenses associated with implementation, assessing expected cash flows and revenues, and evaluating overall financial sustainability. It also requires mapping available funding opportunities and financial schemes that can support development and implementation, considering both public and private sources.

¹⁰⁴ CCRI, "Methodology for the implementation of a circular economy at the local and regional scale," European Union, LIFE Programme. [Online]. Available: https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/life_en

8 Good Practices

This chapter presents good practices of financing schemes for the circular economy. The good practices were selected in an effort to show the diversity of financing sources, methods and regional distribution in Europe. However, it should not be hidden that a key criterion for their selection was the availability of information.

8.1 CIRCWASTE (Finland)

Demonstrating the collaboration between 20 partners, the “LIFE IP on waste - towards circular economy in Finland” (CIRCWASTE) ¹⁰⁵ project running between 01 October 2016 and 31 December 2023, aims to position Finland as a forerunner in circular economy by implementing the country’s National Waste Management Plan. The project is recognised as a good practice by the European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform “because of its intervention methodology, its collaborative capacity, and its results.”¹⁰⁶

Of particular interest is the involvement of 5 research institutes and universities, 12 municipalities and regions, as well as 8 private companies and public enterprises in carrying out 20 project actions across 6 themes, which include:

- Regional strategic development and networking projects,
- Resource efficiency in construction,
- Biodegradable waste and by-flows,
- Industrial waste and material flows,
- Utilising soils, and
- Digital solutions and logistics.

¹⁰⁵ Circwaste, "Materiaalitkiertoon: Towards Circular Economy in Finland," [Online]. Available: <https://www.materiaalitkiertoon.fi/en-US/Circwaste> ; European Commission, LIFE IP on Waste - Towards Circular Economy in Finland, 2023. [Online]. Available:

https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/life/publicWebsite/index.cfm?fuseaction=search.dspPage&n_proj_id=6098

¹⁰⁶ European Union, "Financing the circular economy," [Online]. Available:

<https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/en/financing-circular-economy>

All together, these partners have a total budget of €18,521,507 with an EU contribution of €11,112,904 from the EU LIFE Programme. Nine other Finnish institutions are co-financing the project. This collaborative approach not only in terms of project participants but also in funding, shows that greater success is achieved when multiple stakeholders are involved as the project has helped reach national and EU targets with regard to transitioning to a circular economy.

8.2 URBIOFIN (Greece)

Composed of 15 partners from Spain, Denmark, Belgium, France, Greece and the Netherlands, the URBIOFIN project (Demonstration of an integrated innovative biorefinery for the transformation of Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) into new BioBased products) aims to transform urban solid waste into new bioproducts demonstrated through a biorefinery concept.¹⁰⁷ The project utilized three modules which resulted in the daily conversion of about 10 tonnes of the organic fraction of MSW into chemical building blocks, biopolymers, and additives. Throughout the process, the project utilized green technologies that resulted in an efficient, circular and zero-waste valorisation of what would have been typical organic waste products of a municipality. These project results can make a valuable contribution to raising awareness among potential consumers of the benefits of using biobased products. On one hand, the integrated biorefinery reflects the environmentally friendly image of the new biobased processes, while on the other hand, it also contributes to reducing the organic fraction of waste going to landfills and achieving the objectives of the Waste Framework Directive.

The URBIOFIN project received funding under the Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI JU) within the EU Horizon 2020 programme with a total budget of €15 million. The solutions were implemented from 01 June 2017 to 30 September 2022.

¹⁰⁷ Urbiofin, "Home," [Online]. Available: <https://www.urbiofin.eu/>

8.3. Circular Economy for Businesses (Murcia, Spain)

Murcia is an entrepreneurial Mediterranean region willing to progress towards a sustainable & resilient economic & social development model that creates jobs, wealth and well-being based on business innovation.

At present, the competences in this matter in the region of Murcia pivot on two well-defined administrative arms: on the one hand, environmental circularity, responsibility of the Regional Ministry for environment and Climate and on the other hand, circular economy, which is the responsibility of the Regional Ministry for Business, through the Regional Development Agency (RDA), INFO Murcia.

In order to raise awareness and provide services on sustainability & circular economy to the business ecosystem in the region, some particular initiatives have been carried out by INFO Murcia in cooperation with regional stakeholders over the last years:

Firstly, in the framework of the regional monitoring dashboard, Circular Economy & Business Sustainability of the Murcia Region Observatory¹⁰⁸, the circular economy is currently promoted for sectors identified as "tractors", as well as those with growth potential. In addition to the agro-food and water sectors, the dashboard targets sectors such as tourism, habitat, footwear, among others, also focusing on key areas such as energy, the maritime sector, the chemical sector and Key Enabling Technologies (KETs).

Likewise, there are other tools consisting of webinars: on the one hand, CIRCULARMENTE consists of a Workshop on Circular Economy and opportunities for companies, held on 15/10/2024, conceived as an annual event to be organized in the frame of the EU Annual Circular Economy conference. Moreover, World Pact United Nations (UN) webinars explore business opportunities emerging from SDGs (one conference and 4 webinars from mid-2023 up to October 2024).

¹⁰⁸ Looparm, "Looparm." [Online]. Available: <https://looparm.es/>

Besides that, access for companies to Murcia region office in Brussels has been allowed, implementation as partner of EU funded projects on Circular Economy¹⁰⁹ encouraged, assessment service on sustainability & circular economy for businesses¹¹⁰ provided, as well as self-diagnosis on sustainability for businesses.¹¹¹ Finally, regarding financial support to SMEs, there are initiatives for sustainability voucher providing grants for businesses to calculate carbon footprint (company and product & service), water footprint and eco-design, as well as energy efficiency for companies.

Likewise, by opening new business opportunities, circular economy promotes innovation and economic diversification, which can lead to job creation and the strengthening of business sector in the region of Murcia. That is why the next challenge now is adopting a comprehensive Business Circular Roadmap, to help our businesses in a more structured and efficient way. For that reason, INFO Murcia has recently applied to the Joint Research Center (JRC) call entitled “Preparatory Action: Innovation for place-based transformation”¹¹²

Counting on the support of EU Preparatory Action, INFO Murcia is expected to work and receive training & guidance on circular economy for businesses and commit to a new policy output in the Murcia region, that is to say, a Roadmap for businesses on Sustainability & Circular Economy 2025-2027, under the framework of Enterprise Europe Network (EEN) Seimed (in coordination with regional business stakeholders). In that sense, the main headings are raising awareness & Information, training, assessment, financial support, and governance, technological surveillance & prospective.

Circular Roadmap aims to provide support services to SMEs as target beneficiaries of such a scheme, with a view to integrating circular economy into their business models. To achieve so, INFO Murcia is enrolling the most relevant actors in business support & circular economy

¹⁰⁹ i.e. see Agro2Circular, “Agro2Circular.” [Online]. Available: <https://agro2circular.eu/>

¹¹⁰ Seimed, “Sostenibilidad.” [Online]. Available: <https://www.seimed.eu/page/sostenibilidad>

¹¹¹ Instituto Fomento Murcia, “Sostenibilidad Empresarial,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.institutofomentomurcia.es/web/portal/sostenibilidadempresarial>

¹¹² European Commission, *Call For Expression Of Interest To Participate In The Preparatory Action For “Innovation For Place-Based Transformation”*. [Online]. Available: https://place-based-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/551255f2-4ebe-44ba-b53b-e76edbc163ca_en?filename=Call%20for%20EoI%20EUPA%20Innovation%20for%20place-based%20transformation.pdf

in the region as beneficiaries of such a double component aimed to facilitate learning & readiness to implement place-based transformation, in particular:

- INFO Murcia as public leader for business innovation.
- Regional Ministry in charge of environment and climate, as public supporter.
- Technology centers in sectors related to circular economy, in particular Cetec (plastics), CTNC (agrofood) and Cetenma (energy & environment), as supporters from private sector.
- The Circular Economy chairs from the two public universities (UMU and/or UPCT), as supporters from regional academia.
- The general association of companies in the region (Croem), the largest business federation.

Innovative business models play a crucial role as essential drivers in this transformation towards circular economy, and for that reason, it is imperative that businesses, administrations and citizens are actively involved. Indeed, given that companies need to adapt, these changes will not only boost the incorporation of the circular economy in their strategies, but they will also produce tangible economic and environmental benefits. In fact, according to the World Business Council for Sustainable Development, 93% of European companies consider the circular economy to be crucial to their future success, and 85% plan to invest in this approach, a fact that confirms the relevance of such model for the welfare of the economy.

Therefore, with a bold vision and concrete actions in favor of the circularity of the economy, the Region of Murcia is ready to strengthen its business sector, generate competitive advantages in the medium and long term and lead the way towards a more prosperous and sustainable future for its population.

8.4. EIB Financed Projects

8.4.1. Novamont Renewable Chemistry, Italy

The project involves the financing of investments for the development of an integrated supply chain in the field of biochemicals and bioplastics. The EIB's proposed financing

amounts to some €30 million. The project concerns the use of innovative process technologies to produce bioplastics and biochemicals to be used for a range of applications in industry (e.g., plasticisers, biodegradable lubricating oils for industry and vehicles) and consumer goods (e.g., renewable and biodegradable bases for cosmetics, carrier bags, films and packaging).¹¹³

8.4.2. ISP Loan for Circular Economy, Italy

The scheme allows circular economy projects to be implemented by SMEs and mid-cap companies through a framework loan. To receive co-financing, projects must demonstrate the use of different circular business models that aim to, as an example, preserve the value of products and materials for as long as possible and minimise resource consumption and waste generation.¹¹⁴ These projects are to be implemented in different sectors such as food, energy, mobility, fashion, built environment, consumer goods and industrial manufacturing.

8.4.3. IREN Climate Action and Circular Economy Loan, Italy

The programme focuses on the financing of projects on the solid waste and hydropower sectors.¹¹⁵ These projects are thus considered as investments on efforts to counteract climate change and promote circularity.

Specifically, investments on projects related to solid waste management will be implemented in the regions of Liguria, Piedmont and Reggio Emilia. Examples of financed actions include, among others, a plant to produce pallets from wood waste and the purchase of new vehicles for waste collection. Additionally, investments in the hydropower sector were implemented in 16 sites in the Piedmont and Campania regions.

¹¹³ European Investment Bank, "Novamont Renewable Chemistry," 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://www.eib.org/en/projects/pipelines/all/20150447>

¹¹⁴ European Investment Bank, "ISP Loan for Circular Economy," 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.eib.org/en/projects/pipelines/all/20180715>

¹¹⁵ European Investment Bank, "IREN Climate Action & Circular Economy Loan," 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.eib.org/en/projects/pipelines/all/20190156>

8.4.4. Winnow, Romania

The food waste management company, Winnow, will develop and introduce EIB funds worth EUR7.5m for the development of software and hardware solutions to help staff in commercial kitchens to reduce the amount and type of food wasted. The aim is to provide users with data for the management and prevention of food waste.

As part of the European Growth Finance Facility (EGFF), the loan scheme is designed to offer SMEs and mid-cap companies' investment in tangible and intangible assets thus achieving a positive crowding-in effect, attracting additional private investors to the companies.¹¹⁶

8.4.5. Tackling Food Waste, France

Straying away from traditional food waste practices of paying other companies to either burn or dispose of unsold products in landfills, the French company, Phenix, has developed an innovative and digital alternative. The service allows companies to sell their food items just before its expiry date as well as help provide food donations to charities.¹¹⁷ This scheme ensures that no food is wasted while money is saved not only on the food item itself but also with its waste disposal. This idea has also given businesses financial incentives such as tax credits when they donate to charities. Phenix has expanded their services to Portugal and Spain, but their idea has also received investments from Bpifrance in order to internationalize and grow further.

8.5. De Clique (Netherlands)

De Clique is a Dutch company that collects food by-products, such as coffee grounds and other food waste from companies, to resell them to third party suppliers and product manufacturers who transform them into new products such as food ingredients, cosmetics

¹¹⁶ European Investment Bank, "Romania: Investment Plan for Europe - Support to Improve Food Management," 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.eib.org/en/press/all/2019-251-investment-plan-for-europe-support-to-improve-food-management-in-romania>

¹¹⁷ European Investment Bank, Joint Initiative on Circular Economy [Factsheet], 2019. [Online]. Available: https://www.eib.org/attachments/joint_initiative_on_circular_economy_en.pdf

and biomaterials. In order to be more environmentally friendly, the collection process is carried out by bicycle couriers and electric vehicles. On the alternative, inedible food by-products and other organic waste are often landfilled or incinerated. Thus, the company guarantees the reuse of materials by collecting and separating waste into high-value products that last in the community economy.

Currently, it is estimated that only 2% of organic waste produced in cities is reused to make valuable products, which is a large untapped potential opportunity. This system helps to increase this figure to 10 tons per month by reducing dependence on finite resources.

8.6. GPP Good Practices

8.6.1. GPP in Flemish Governments Cooperation Agreement with Municipalities

During the years 2008-2013, the Flemish Department of Environment, Nature and Energy awarded grants to the municipalities that signed a cooperation agreement. Additional grants could be obtained on a voluntary basis through actions at the award or project level¹¹⁸. One of the ten topics covered was optimal ecological use, including the sustainable use of wood, certified waste in tenders and passive awareness. On the procurement level, environmentally friendly products should be used and promoted to the target groups (product groups are as follows: Compost, construction waste, materials from recycled plastics, office supplies, catering, environmentally friendly products, cleaning products, wood preservatives, paints and varnishes, products from recognized recycling points). GPP guidelines have been developed for those product groups. The projects approved were eligible for 50% funding. The evaluation was based on annual reports. For many municipalities, this marked the beginning of green procurement in their organization.

€30,000,000 in subsidies were needed. The number of grants depended on the inhabitants and the area of the municipality. The basis was €1.7/hour + €1.4/ha (minimum €20,000).

¹¹⁸ Interreg Europe, "GPP in Flemish Governments Cooperation Agreement with Municipalities," 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.interregeurope.eu/good-practices/gpp-in-flemish-governments-cooperation-agreement-with-municipalities>

The subsidy was €30,000 x the maximum number of full-time sustainability workers specified in the contract. Projects received €1.7/hour + €1.4/ha x 61.1%.¹¹⁹

8.6.2. GPP Regional Plan, Liguria

The new Green Public Procurement Plan is based on the previous strategy and was developed to raise awareness of the circular economy and its application in the regional market by increasing the participation of SMEs in tenders and improving their knowledge of green certifications.¹²⁰ The main objective is to implement green procurement by including CAM (minimum environmental criteria) in public tenders for goods and services. This innovative plan includes training for both the public administration and the private sector. On the one hand, regarding public administration side, this project aims to promote capacity building for the preparation and evaluation of green tenders. On the other hand, the private sector, for its part, will promote capacity building in companies for environmental sustainability criteria and certification. Under this framework, SMEs will have to acquire knowledge and adopt European sustainability tools such as EMAS, PEF, EU ECOLABEL and LCA studies. In fact, the existence of those EU instruments, in particular EMAS, is rewarded in the evaluation of tenders. The plan promotes the use of European sustainability instruments to foster the recovery and increase the resilience of SMEs and the regional and national market after the Covid-19 pandemic.

The project and its entire implementation required about 35,000 euros and the participation of 4 members. The rest of the additional activities such as stakeholder meetings, training, etc. required about 15,000 euros and the hiring of 2 staff.¹²¹

¹¹⁹ Vlaanderen Department Omgeving, "Home," [Online]. Available: <https://omgeving.vlaanderen.be/nl>

¹²⁰ Interreg Europe, "Enhance and the New GPP Plan of the Liguria Region," [Online]. Available: <https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/enhance/news/newsarticle/14499/enhance-and-the-new-gpp-plan-of-the-liguria-region/>

¹²¹ Interreg Europe, *Untitled Document*. [Online]. Available: https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/tx_tevprojects/library/file_1655473732.pdf

8.6.3. Promotion of Green Public Procurement by Providing Green Technical Specifications, Lithuania

The Central Procurement Organisation (CPO LT) is the body in charge of procurement, both at the national and local level, on behalf of the contracting authorities.¹²² Acquisitions are conducted through the CPO LT electronic catalogue, which minimizes the procurement procedure, optimizes the purchasing cycles, and reduce the costs of the process. This is structured into 49 different groups within the categories of services, goods and works.

Through this methodology, it is possible to determine which technical specifications are necessary to qualify for green public procurement. This facilitates the process of green public procurement, as it is not necessary for the contracting organizations to establish the criteria themselves. In addition, these entities have the possibility to use these technical specifications as an example and carry out this process themselves.

99% of procurements are carried out using green specifications. There are 380 ecological specifications for categories such as office supplies, cleaning services, IT and office equipment, cell phones, furniture, and foodstuffs.

During the first half of 2020, ecological goods and services acquired through the CPO LT e-catalogue achieved a total value of €18 million.¹²³

8.6.4. Good Practices in Green Public Procurement in Regional Waste Management, Spain

The *Consortio para la Gestión de Residuos de Vinalopó* (CREA) oversees waste management in the districts of Vinalopó, Spain. One of the main environmental problems is the huge amount of waste that is landfilled and cannot be recycled.¹²⁴ As a solution, CREA aims to reduce the amount of waste by recycling and classifying the waste generated for subsequent recovery or reintroduction into the value chain. This project is particularly

¹²² CPO Lithuania, "EU Support," [Online]. Available: <https://www2.cpo.lt/en/eu-support/>

¹²³ Interreg Europe, "Promotion of Green Public Procurement by Providing Green Technical Specifications," 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.interregeurope.eu/good-practices/promotion-of-green-public-procurement-by-providing-green-technical-specifications>

¹²⁴ Crea Consorci de Residus, "El reto del reciclaje," [Online]. Available: <https://elretodelreciclaje.com/crea-consorci-de-residus/>

essential in densely populated areas, where there are environmental problems related to poor waste management and uncontrolled landfills. All municipalities are required to have an environmental plan that includes green procurement measures tailored to the needs and reality of the municipality.

8.7. Good Financial Practices of Banks in the Region of Murcia

The following analysis provides an overview of some financial practices adopted by five prominent banks in the Region of Murcia, Spain, with a particular focus on their contributions to the circular economy. These institutions have demonstrated a strong commitment to sustainable finance by developing innovative products and services that promote environmental stewardship and resource efficiency. While the data presented is derived from publicly available sources, it is essential to note that the banking landscape is dynamic, and specific initiatives may evolve over time.

8.7.1. Cajamar Cooperative Group

Cajamar Cooperative Group¹²⁵, a cornerstone of the agricultural community, has demonstrated a strong commitment to sustainability. By offering innovative financial solutions, the group is fostering a greener future and aligning its practices with the principles of the circular economy. The group has several key initiatives, from which it is worthy to highlight the following:

- **Financing Sustainable Projects:** Cajamar is actively funding projects that promote sustainable practices, such as organic farming, precision agriculture, and renewable energy. The bank has also made significant investments in modernizing irrigation systems, thereby contributing to water efficiency.

¹²⁵ Cajamar, *Sustainability Report*. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bcc.es/es/responsabilidad-corporativa/memoria-anual-rsc/>

- **Supporting SMEs and Mid-caps:** The group provides financing to SMEs and mid-cap companies, particularly those operating in rural areas and the agri-food sector. This support fosters the development of a more sustainable and resilient economy.
- **International Partnerships:** Cajamar's collaboration with the EIB signifies a commitment to international cooperation and best practices in sustainable finance. In 2023, a €350 million covered bond issuance, facilitated by the EIB, enabled Cajamar to allocate up to €784 million to support investments by SMEs and mid-caps in rural areas, and an additional €196 million to accelerate the green transition.

Moreover, Cajamar has also established a comprehensive framework that encompasses best practices across the following key areas:

- **Project Evaluation and Selection:** The bank has implemented a rigorous evaluation process involving qualified experts to ensure that projects align with sustainability goals. Moreover, projects are continuously monitored and adapted to maintain their sustainability over time.
- **Risk Management:** Cajamar proactively identifies and mitigates environmental and social risks, ensuring that its financing activities contribute to a more sustainable future.
- **Management of Proceeds:** The bank has established a clear policy for managing the proceeds from sustainable finance initiatives, ensuring that funds are allocated to projects that generate positive environmental and social impacts.
- **Transparency and Reporting:** Cajamar is committed to transparency and accountability, publishing annual reports on the allocation of proceeds and the impact of its sustainable finance initiatives.

By adopting these best practices, Cajamar Cooperative Group has solidified its position as a leader in sustainable finance. The group's commitment to the circular economy, combined with its innovative financial solutions and international partnerships, is driving positive change and contributing to a more sustainable future.

8.7.2. CaixaBank

A pioneer in sustainable finance in Spain, CaixaBank¹²⁶ is leading the charge in the Region of Murcia with a wide range of green financial products and services:

- Energy Efficiency Loans: CaixaBank offers preferential interest rates for loans to businesses and individuals investing in energy efficiency improvements.
- Sustainable Investment Funds: Beyond the "CaixaBank Sostenible" fund, the bank has a range of options focused on sectors like renewable energy, green buildings, and sustainable water management.
- Circular Economy Advisory Services: CaixaBank provides consulting services to help companies identify circular economy opportunities and develop sustainable business models.

8.7.3. BBVA

With a global reach and a strong local presence, BBVA¹²⁷ is empowering businesses and individuals in Murcia to make sustainable choices through its comprehensive suite of green financial solutions. The next specific financial products represent clear examples of how BBVA is supporting the transition to a circular economy in the Region of Murcia.¹²⁸

- Green Mortgages: BBVA offers green mortgages with preferential conditions for purchasing or renovating energy-efficient homes.
- Circular Economy Partnerships: The bank has partnered with local governments and universities to promote circular economy initiatives, such as waste reduction and recycling programs.
- Sustainable Supply Chain Financing: BBVA supports businesses in developing more sustainable supply chains through financing and advisory services.

¹²⁶ CaixaBank, "Caixabank." [Online]. Available: https://www.caixabank.es/particular/home/particulares_es.html

¹²⁷ BBVA, "BBVA Compass." [Online]. Available: <https://www.bbva.com/en/specials/bbva-compass/>

¹²⁸ Ibid.

8.7.4. Unicaja Banco

Committed to a greener tomorrow, Unicaja Banco is supporting businesses and individuals in Murcia to adopt eco-friendly practices through its innovative financial products and initiatives. The subsequent products and initiatives will showcase the bank's commitment to sustainability and its impact on the region.

- **Eco-Efficiency Loans:** Unicaja Banco offers competitive interest rates for businesses investing in energy-efficient technologies, such as LED lighting, insulation, and renewable energy systems.
- **Sustainable Investment Funds:** The bank has a range of investment funds focused on ESG factors, aligning with the principles of the circular economy.
- **Carbon Footprint Reduction Initiatives:** Unicaja Banco is committed to reducing its own carbon footprint through measures such as paperless offices and energy-efficient buildings.

9 Financing Recommendations

9.1. Circular Economy Overview & Challenges

- It must be noted that according to the Circularity Gap Report 2024, the world economy is currently just 7.2% circular, a number that has been declining annually. Even though the circular economy has become a "megatrend," lofty ideals and objectives are still not being translated into tangible actions and quantifiable effects on the ground. For that reason, a well-executed circular economy, on the other hand, could drastically lessen this effect by using 70% fewer resources to meet human needs than we do now.
- The circular economy concept is inherently a multi-stakeholder approach that involves many processes. Therefore, giving high priority to stakeholder participation and collective collaboration in the formulation of projects will help them gain clout and attract more funding.
- Cooperation between actors in the field of the environment or circular economy is called to be a line of work for the present and for the future. Companies can use the sub-products of other firms, which will enable cooperation between companies that had always presented cultural barriers, at least in Spain (win-win approach).
- The private sector should not be forced to share or promote sustainability but rather reinforce the idea that it should be based above all on business opportunities rather than just legal obligation or conviction. Not harming the environment or the climate is not just a matter of corporate social responsibility but also a business opportunity for the private sector.

9.2. Financing & Investment for Circular Economy

- Given the intricate nature of securing financing for circular business models, engaging a specialized advisory service is strongly recommended to navigate the complexities of the current financial landscape.

- The creation of reporting standards for circular businesses and the adoption of some standardised reporting measures would reduce asymmetric information and distortions that hinder the growth of circular investments.
- The search for financing opportunities for the circular economy should not be limited to government support or incentives but should also consider different business models, loans, and private sector support. Although public funding is widely available in this area, it is not possible to finance all projects. Business models with a high sustainability contribution can receive funding from the private sector through a win-win relationship.
- It is also possible to find investments in innovative ideas with alternative mechanisms such as crowdfunding, as small investors can use such mechanisms to make all their investments. Moreover, a business idea can be promoted at the same time thanks to the large audience it reaches.
- If there are no grant opportunities for investments in the circular economy or if there is no suitable programme at regular intervals, the loans granted by investment banks or private banks should be considered. Since such loans are supported by certain consortia or the public sector, they offer the chance to find financing that is more suitable than the market conditions.
- When looking for funding for projects, it is useful for companies to find the right fund if they first define the focus of their activities. This is because each programme has its own priorities and funding mechanisms. For example, if the project idea is more of a research and modelling project or a pilot application, it would make sense to use the tendering opportunities of the Horizon Europe programme.
- The legal status of a project organisation can affect the use of the programmes. Some programmes are only suitable for public institutions or non-governmental organisations, while others are suitable for for-profit organisations. When applying for the programmes, those criteria need to be checked.
- The lack of credible commitments from the public sector poses a risk to long-term investment decisions by private sector actors that need to be addressed.

- To redirect financial resources from linear to circular solutions, negative externalities need to be systematically priced in as circular businesses would benefit from corresponding price signals.

9.3. Business Models & Market Considerations

- When developing business models for the circular economy, the positive and negative effects of incentives in the market and financial analysis need to be considered. The reason behind that lies in the additional support received for transactions during the operational process, which may shorten the return on investments. On the contrary, business models may become less profitable due to additional obstacles they encounter.
- The recycling and upcycling rate of organic products is still very low, which means that there is still a long way to go in this area, which holds investment potential. If considering the principles of waste prevention, sharing systems, and the win-win principle when developing business models, they will have a high chance of success and minimize harm to nature.

9.4. Role of Technology & Innovation in Circular Economy

- The importance of technological partners (i.e., technological centres and other research and technology organisations) promoting technology and knowledge transfer and the implementation of new methods, advanced materials, and improved processes in enterprises, in order to accelerate industrial transition towards a green economy.

9.5. Investment Priorities for Sustainability

- Investments should contribute to the extension of product life cycles and the reuse of waste and the valorisation of sub-products in line with EU regulations to support the transition to a circular economy.

- Investments should contribute to reducing and optimising water resources so that adequate ecological levels are maintained in aquifers and basins.
- Investments should contribute to reducing all forms of pollution that negatively impact ecosystems and human health.
- Investments should contribute to protecting or restoring biodiversity and achieving good ecosystem status.

9.6. Green Public Procurement (GPP) & Sustainable Procurement

- GPP is also a kind of incentive and an important tool for actors to achieve a positive external impact on nature. Public institutions can use their purchasing power to put pressure on suppliers to achieve positive environmental impacts through GPP.
- Suppliers should comply with GPP criteria as soon as possible to stay ahead of the competition because the number of institutions requiring these criteria is increasing by the day. Many environmentally friendly applications that are preferred today will be mandatory tomorrow.
- Environmental aspects and opportunities to apply green procurement criteria should be considered in all procurement processes, especially in terms of reducing energy consumption (electricity, heat, and water) and emissions (CO₂ emissions and particulates), recyclability, life extension, material selection, use of recycled materials, and waste prevention.
- Possibilities for buying used products and products made from recycled materials should be considered.
- The products procured should be recyclable and sent for reuse or recycling after use.
- Life-cycle costs should be taken into account in procurement. This allows procurers to choose the most economically advantageous option on a life-cycle basis.

- Resource-efficient procurement options should be considered. These include the procurement of services instead of products, optional forms of ownership, and the reuse of products.
- Eco-label criteria can be used when formulating tenders.

10 Conclusions

This deliverable has examined the financial mechanisms available for supporting circular economy projects, highlighting the range of funding schemes that exist at European, national, and regional levels. The analysis demonstrates that while there are numerous financial opportunities—including EU grants, regional public funds, and private-sector instruments such as green bonds and crowdfunding—access to finance remains a critical barrier for many circular economy initiatives. The funding ecosystem is expanding, and policies such as green public procurement are increasingly helping redirect capital from linear to circular economic models.

Despite this, circular businesses, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises, often struggle to secure financial support due to perceived risks, long return-on-investment periods, and the absence of standardized metrics for evaluating their viability. Many traditional financial institutions are still hesitant to invest in circular economy ventures due to a lack of clear benchmarks for profitability and risk assessment. However, growing awareness of sustainability and the economic potential of circular business models presents significant opportunities. Investors and policymakers are progressively recognizing the long-term value of circular solutions, leading to an increase in targeted financial products and policy support mechanisms.

The recommendations provided in this report play a crucial role in bridging the gap between existing financing schemes and the needs of circular businesses. Aligning financial incentives with environmental goals, standardizing reporting frameworks, expanding advisory support services, and fostering collaboration between public and private entities are key measures that can enhance financial accessibility and effectiveness. Implementing these actions will help mitigate the barriers currently preventing many circular businesses from accessing the funding they need to scale and sustain their operations.

Financing is a fundamental driver of adoption, scalability, and long-term sustainability for circular economy business models. Without sufficient financial backing, even the most innovative circular solutions may remain confined to small-scale applications or fail to reach their full potential. A well-structured and inclusive financial system is essential to support the

transition from linear to circular practices, enabling businesses to invest in infrastructure, technology, and human capital. Strengthening financing mechanisms is not just about funding individual projects; it is about reinforcing a broader economic shift towards sustainability, resilience, and long-term environmental and economic benefits. By addressing current financial challenges and leveraging existing opportunities, circular economy initiatives can achieve greater impact, ensuring a more resource-efficient and sustainable future.

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